

Derivation of HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs)

for Cadmium: HBM-GV_{GenPop} for the general

population & HBM-GV_{Worker} for workers

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2 Glossary

α 1M	Alpha-1 microglobulin
β 2M	Beta-2 microglobulin
ACGIH	American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists
ADME	Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion
AF	Assessment Factor
ANSES	French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health & Safety
ATSDR	Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry
BAL	Biological Action Level
BEI	Biological Exposure Index
BfR	German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment
BGV	Biological Guidance Value
B-Cd	Blood Cadmium
BLV	Biological Limit Value
BMD	Benchmark Dose
BMDL	Benchmark Dose Lower confidence Limit
CEI	Cumulative exposure index
Cd	Cadmium
CI95%	95% confidence intervals
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging
CNS	Central nervous system
Creat	Creatinine
DFG	German Research Foundation
DG Empl	Commission's Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion
EAA	Environment Agency Austria
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EU	European Union
FEV ₁	Forced Expiratory Volume in one second
FIOH	Finnish Institute of Occupational Health
IARC	International Agency for Research on Cancer
ICP-MS	Inductively Coupled Plasma Mass Spectrometry
INSA	Instituto Nacional de Saúde Dr. Ricardo Jorge

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ISCIII	Institute of Health Carlos III
IUPAC	International Union on Pure and Applied Chemistry
IQ	Intelligence Quotient
HBM-GV	HBM Guidance Value
HBM	Human Biomonitoring
HBM4EU	European Biomonitoring Initiative
HSE	Health and Safety Executive
HMWP	High Molecular Weight Protein
GFR	Glomerular Filtration Rate
LANUV NRW	Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz Nordrhein-Westfalen (State Office for Nature, Environment and Consumer Protection North Rhine-Westphalia)
LMWP	Low Molecular Weight Protein
LO(A)EL	Lowest Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
MAK	Maximale Arbeitsplatz-Konzentration
MT	Metallothionein
NAG	N-acetyl-beta-D-glucosaminidase
NO(A)EL	No Observed (Adverse) Effect Level
OEL	Occupational Exposure Limit
POD	Point of departure
PBPK/PBTK	Physiologically Based Pharmacokinetic/Toxicokinetic
PNS	Peripheral nervous system
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals
RBP	Retinol-binding protein
SCAHT	Swiss Centre for Applied Human Toxicology
TWA	Time-weighted average
U-Cd	Urinary cadmium
UBA	Umweltbundesamt (German Environment Agency)
VITO	Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek (Flemish Institute for Technological Research)

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3 Introduction

3.1 Objectives

Within the framework of Task 5.2 of HBM4EU, HBM guidance values (HBM-GVs) are derived for HBM4EU priority substances.

The methodology applied to derive these values is based on the procedure described in the German Human Biomonitoring Commission's position paper (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2014, Apel et al., 2017) and in the guidance document elaborated by the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES) for the derivation of biological limit values (BLVs) for chemicals used in the workplace (ANSES, 2014). These methodological approaches have been summarised and combined in a concept document previously released in the HBM4EU Task 5.2 workframe (HBM4EU concept paper).

In the current report, HBM-GVs for the general population (HBM-GV_{GenPop}) and HBM-GVs for occupationally exposed adults (HBM-GV_{Worker}) are derived and discussed for Cadmium (Cd). The values established are based on the nephrotoxic effects of Cd.

3.2 Methodological aspects of the HBM-GVs derivation for Cadmium

Cd is a well-studied substance of relevance to environmental health in terms of its cumulative and carcinogenic properties for which extensive literature exists. A detailed overview of the studies is provided e.g. by the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA, 2009), the German Human Biomonitoring Commission (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011), the Agency for Toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR, 2012), the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES, 2018) and by the International Union on Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC, 2018).

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4 General properties of the substance of concern

4.1 Identification of the substance

Cd is a heavy metal found as an environmental contaminant both through natural occurrence and from industrial and agricultural sources (use of Cd-containing sewage sludge or phosphorous as fertilizer).

Elemental Cd vapour is rapidly oxidised in air to produce Cd oxide. Gases or vapours like carbon dioxide, water vapour, sulfur dioxide, sulfur trioxide and hydrogen chloride react with elemental Cd to form salts that may enter environmental media. Cd forms many inorganic salts (IUPAC, 2018).

The main Cd compounds found in industry are presented in Table 1 (IUPAC, 2018 and ECHA, 2015).

Table 1: Main compounds of Cd used in industry

Name	Cd metal	Cd dichloride	Cd oxide	Cd sulfate	Cd sulfide	Cd nitrate	Cd hydroxide	Cd zinc sulfide Yellow* (Pigments Yellow 35)	Cd selenide Red* (Pigments Red 108)
CAS number	7440-43-9	10108-64-2	1306-19-0	10124-36-4	1306-23-6	10325-94-7	21041-95-2	8048-07-5	58339-34-7
EINECS number	231-152-8	233-296-7	215-146-2	233-331-6	215-147-8	233-710-6	244-168-5	232-466-8	261-218-1
Formula	Cd	CdCl ₂	CdO	CdSO ₄	CdS	Cd(NO ₃) ₂	Cd(OH) ₂	Cd _(1-x) Zn _x S	CdS _(1-x) Se _x

* generic identifiers which may eventually cover multiple substances

4.2 Physico-chemical properties

Table 2 summarises the physico-chemical properties for Cd and selected Cd compounds (IUPAC, 2018; ATDSR, 2012, ECHA website²).

Table 2: Cd metal and Cd compounds physico-chemical properties

Name	Cd metal	Cd chloride	Cd oxide	Cd sulfate	Cd sulfide	Cd nitrate	Cd hydroxide	Cd zinc sulfide Yellow (Pigments Yellow 35)	Cd selenide Red (Pigments Red 108)
Molecular mass	112.4	183.3	128.4	208.5	144.5	236.4	146.4	Variable depending on Zn/Se content	
Appearance	Grey/silver-white solid	White hygroscopic solid	Brown or red ochre powder	White hygroscopic solid ^a	Orange ochre powder	White hygroscopic solid	White crystalline solid/greenish-white powder	Bright yellow powder	Brightly coloured from yellow-orange through red to red-deep maroon

² <https://echa.europa.eu/> (consulted in August 2019)

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Name	Cd metal	Cd chloride	Cd oxide	Cd sulfate	Cd sulfide	Cd nitrate	Cd hydroxide	Cd zinc sulfide Yellow (Pigment s Yellow 35)	Cd sulfoselenide Red (Pigments Red 108)
Melting point (°C)	321	568	950	1000	871-890	360	130 ^b		
Boiling point (°C)	765-767	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
Vapour pressure	Negligible (25°C)	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA		
Density at 20°C (g.cm ⁻³)	8.6	4.1 (at 25°C)	6.9 ^c	4.7	4.8	3.6	4.8		
Solubility in water at 20°C (mg.L ⁻¹)	Insoluble	Soluble	Insoluble	soluble	Soluble at 1.3 mg.L ⁻¹ at 18°C	NA	0.026 ^d	Practical-ly insoluble	Practical-ly insoluble

^a green liquid as given on ECHA website (in air)

^b 188 °C as given on ECHA website

^c 8.26 as given on ECHA website

^d 0.007 as given on ECHA website

4.3 Uses of the substance

Cd compounds are mainly used (Kommisson Human-Biomonitoring, 2011; IUPAC, 2018):

- for plating of steel and iron (rust-protecting coating);
- as plastic stabilizer;
- as pigments in a wide variety of applications, including engineering plastics, glass, ceramics, rubber, enamels artists' colours and fireworks;
- in electrode material in nickel-Cd batteries;
- in low-melting alloys in thin film solar panels.

4.4 Human exposure

Cd is found naturally in low concentrations, usually combined with zinc and lead as sulphide ores (IUPAC 2018). It occurs in the environment in its inorganic form as a result of volcanic emissions and weathering of rocks. However, anthropogenic sources have increased the background levels of Cd in soil, water and living organisms. Cd is released into the environment by wastewater and waste incineration, and contamination of agricultural soils can occur by the use of fertilizers, by air deposition and by Cd-containing sewage sludge (EFSA, 2009). There is a widespread contamination of soil in many areas of the world, from various natural geological sources, and from pollution by Cd-containing fertilizers or industrial emissions (IUPAC, 2018).

Human exposure to Cd is occurring mostly via the respiratory and the gastrointestinal tracts. Important non-industrial sources of exposure are cigarette smoke and food, since Cd is taken up by plants. A high Cd content in tobacco leaves and a comparatively high absorption of Cd via the lungs results in a substantially higher concentration of Cd in blood and urine in smokers compared to never-smokers. Blood Cd (B-Cd) in smokers may be up to five times higher compared to never-

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smokers). Each cigarette contains on average 1-2 μ g depending on the origin of the tobacco (EFSA, 2009).

In the non-smoking general population, food accounts for approximately 90% of Cd exposure (mainly from cereals and vegetables) and less than 10% is due to inhalation of the low concentrations of Cd in ambient air and through drinking water. The rate of Cd uptake in crops is influenced principally by the Cd chemical forms present, the soil physico-chemical properties and the plant species (EFSA, 2009). To calculate lifetime Cd dietary exposure, EFSA (2012) estimated a weekly average at 2.04 μ g/kg bw and a potential 95th percentile at 3.66 μ g/kg body weight (EFSA, 2012).

The mining, smelting and industrial usage of Cd has caused considerable exposure of workers to Cd, but it is now fairly well controlled in long-established industrialised countries. There are still problems in developing countries and in some newly industrialised countries (IUPAC, 2018). In processes that involve extremely high temperatures (e.g., the iron and steel industries), Cd can volatilise and be emitted as vapour (EFSA, 2009).

The following people are at particular risk (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011):

- Long-term heavy smokers;
- Individuals who have consumed foods with high Cd contents over several years;
- Individuals (mainly women), who as a result of a chronic deficiency of calcium and iron, have an increased uptake of Cd from the gastrointestinal tract;
- Individuals exposed to Cd in the workplace over a long period of time.

4.5 Classification

Under the Classification, Labelling and Packaging (CLP) regulation, Cd (metal) has a harmonised classification as carcinogenic Category 1B, mutagenic Category 2 and reprotoxic Category 2³, among others. There is also a harmonised classification for some Cd compounds, as summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Harmonised CLP classification of Cd and Cd compounds⁴

Cd metal	Cd dichloride	Cd oxide	Cd sulfate	Cd sulfide	Cd nitrate	Cd hydroxide
Carc.1B (H350) Mut.2 (H341) Repr.2 (H361fd)	Carc.1B (H350) Mut.1B (H340) Repr.1B (H360 FD)	Carc.1B (H350) Mut.2 (H341) Repr.2 (H361fd)	Carc.1B (H350) Mut.1B (H340) Repr.1B (H360 FD)	Carc.1B (H350) Mut.2 (H341) Repr.2 (H361fd)	Carc.1B (H350) Mut.1B (H340)	Carc.1B (H350) Mut.1B (H340)

According to IARC, there is sufficient evidence that Cd and its compounds are carcinogenic to humans (Group 1). There is sufficient evidence that occupational exposure to Cd compounds is associated with an increased risk of lung cancer, but inconsistent (or limited) evidence that Cd exposure increases risks of prostate or kidney cancers (IARC 2012).

³ ECHA website : <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database/-/discli/details/51061> (consulted on december 2018)

⁴ ECHA website : excel table containing all updates to the harmonised classification and labelling of hazardous substances, which are available in Table 3 of Annex VI to the CLP Regulation <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/information-on-chemicals/annex-vi-to-clp> (consulted on december 2018)

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4.6 EU legislation and regulations

The use of Cd and Cd compounds is severely restricted and certain applications are restricted. They are listed in annex XVII of the REACH regulation⁵.

Some compounds as e.g. Cd, Cd oxide, Cd sulfide, Cd sulfate, Cd dichloride, Cd fluoride, Cd carbonate, Cd hydroxide and Cd nitrate are identified as Substances of Very High Concern (SVHCs)⁶ and included in the REACH Candidate list for authorisation.

Fertilizers made from phosphate rock naturally contain Cd, and discussions took place in Europe to reduce the level of Cd in these materials. In June 2019, the Parliament, the Council, and the Commission have reached an agreement on the maximum level of Cd allowed in phosphate fertilizers, but the draft European regulation has yet to be approved. The limits for Cd content in "CE marked" phosphate fertilisers will be 60 mg/kg as from the date of application of the regulation (i.e. three years after its entry into force)⁷. It can be reviewed after seven years from its entry into force.

In 2006, the EU commission set maximum levels for cadmium in foodstuffs⁸. The regulation listed foodstuffs that shall not be placed on the market if they contain Cd at a level exceeding the maximum level allowed (i.e. 0.05 mg/kg wet weight for meat (excluding offal) of bovine animals, sheep, pig and poultry, in vegetables and fruit (excluding leaf vegetables, fresh herbs, fungi, stem vegetables, pine nuts, root vegetables and potatoes).

The European Parliament and the Council agreed to a new amendment of the Carcinogens and Mutagens Directive⁹. This new amendment will adopt a limit value of 0.001 mg Cd.m⁻³ (inhalable fraction), after a transitional period of 8 years. During the transitional period (8 years) a value of 4 µg Cd/m³ (inhalable fraction) will be applied. If the value of 0.004 mg Cd.m⁻³ is applied for the respirable fraction during the transitional period a biomonitoring system will be implemented (with a biological limit value for urinary Cadmium not exceeding 0.002 mg.g⁻¹ creat.)

⁵ Commission regulation (EC) No 552/2009 of 22 June 2009, No 494/2011 of 22 May, No 835/2012 of 18 September 2012, No 2016/217 of 16 February 2016 amending Regulation No 1907/2006 of REACH as regards Annex XVII <https://www.echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/3bfef8a3-8c97-4d85-ae0b-ac6827de49a9https://www.echa.europa.eu/documents/10162/3bfef8a3-8c97-4d85-ae0b-ac6827de49a9> (consulted in August 2019)

⁶ ECHA website: <https://echa.europa.eu/fr/candidate-list-table>, consulted on November 2018

⁷ REGULATION (EU) 2019/1009 OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL of 5 June 2019 laying down rules on the making available on the market of EU fertilising products and amending Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 and repealing Regulation (EC) No 2003/2003

⁸ Commission Regulation (EC) No. 1881/2006 of December 2006 setting maximum levels for certain contaminants in foodstuffs <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006R1881&from=EN> (consulted in August 2019)

⁹ Directive EU 2019-983 of The European Parliament and the Council of 5 June 2019 amending Directive 2004/37/EC on the protection of workers from the risks related to exposure to carcinogens or mutagens at work

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5 General toxicological profile

5.1 Toxicokinetics

5.1.1 Absorption

5.1.1.1 Inhalation

The total amount of Cd absorbed by the body via the lungs depends on the particle size and the solubility of the Cd species. Smaller particles can reach the smaller airways and alveoli, and, depending on the particles' solubility, are absorbed and distributed to the rest of the body (ANSES 2018). Studies in animals show that between 7 and 40% of inhaled aerosol of Cd particles is absorbed into blood, the lower value being valid for larger particles with low solubility and the higher values for small particles and for particles with high solubility (IUPAC, 2018). Nordberg et al., (1985) developed a model for the quantification of inhaled absorption. For coarse dust, the proportion of particle-bound Cd deposited in the lungs is approximately 5% of particles > 10 µm in diameter. By contrast, Cd bound to ultrafine particles (<0.1 µm) is retained in the lungs to a percentage of 50 to 60%. Fifty to 100% of the Cd that is deposited in the alveoli will ultimately be absorbed (ATSDR, 2012). The inhalation absorption rate is therefore generally assumed to be 20% to 50% (Fridberg, 1984, Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011).

Most of the inhaled Cd that is transported to the gut via mucociliary clearance is not absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract (Moore et al., 1973; Rusch et al., 1986).

The large differences in B-Cd levels between smokers and non-smokers underline the importance of inhaled absorption for Cd uptake in the general population (EFSA, 2009).

5.1.1.2 Ingestion

Gastrointestinal uptake of Cd is apparently a saturable process with fractional absorption which decreases at high concentrations (EFSA, 2009). The bioavailability of orally-administered Cd is highly dependent on the nature of the particular matrix to which Cd is bound. The average absorption after ingestion is approximately 1-10% (Fridberg, 1984). In addition, sex, age and nutritional status also play major roles. Zinc, iron, calcium and copper deficiencies can lead to increased absorption in the gastrointestinal tract (Berglund et al., 1994). Simultaneous intake of bivalent cations with food lowers the absorption rate of Cd due to competition for the metal ion transporters in the intestinal mucosa (especially for the Divalent Metal Transporter 1) (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011). Epidemiological studies have shown higher B-Cd levels in women of childbearing age and during pregnancy. Åkesson et al. (2002) have concluded that women with low iron stores, especially those with multiple pregnancies, constitute a risk group for health effects of Cd such as osteoporosis. However, after menopause, the sex-specific differences in Cd absorption are no longer as important (Baecklund, 1999).

5.1.2 Distribution and metabolism

Cd is distributed to most organs in the body, but the blood-brain barrier is an efficient protector of the central nervous system. The greatest amounts of Cd are found in the kidneys (especially in the renal cortex) and liver, and to a lesser extent in the bones, muscles and skin. Elevated levels of Cd are also found in the thyroid gland, pancreas and salivary glands (EFSA, 2009).

In the blood, Cd is mainly found in red blood cells. In plasma, it is mainly bound to proteins, with a high molecular weight fraction mostly constituted of albumin-bound Cd and a low molecular weight fraction mostly constituted of metallothionein (MT)-bound Cd (IUPAC 2018). Järup et al. (1983) observed that for 5 formerly exposed workers, the Cd half-life in blood included a fast component (75-128 days) and a slow component (7.4-16 years).

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The Cd-MT complex is freely filtered at the glomerulus and reabsorbed by the proximal tubule; Cd accumulates over time in the cortex. Cd exposure up-regulates the MTs synthesis in the liver and kidneys, which is a protective response to limit toxicity from the free Cd (Cd²⁺). Cd-induced nephrotoxicity is probably due to unbound Cd as the ultimate toxicant (Nomiya and Nomiya, 1986).

Because of its long half-life, the body burden of Cd increases gradually with age (ANSES, 2018). The critical concentration is represented by the Cd burden at which renal tubular cells are no longer able to synthesise enough MT to neutralise free Cd²⁺ produced by lysosomal degradation of Cd-MT (EFSA, 2009).

The route of Cd administration does not appear to affect the MT metabolism in liver and kidney, although inhalation induces lung MT (Glaser et al., 1986; Hart, 1986) and oral exposure induces intestinal MT (Muller et al., 1986).

Cd accumulates in the placenta at levels about 10 times higher than maternal blood cadmium concentration has been observed in Europe and United States (EFSA, 2009). Cd can cross the placenta, but at a low rate (Lauwerys et al., 1978; Lagerkvist et al., 1992). The placenta is therefore only a partial barrier to foetal exposure (Baars et al., 2001). Cd concentration in the cord blood is only around 50 % of the maternal Cd blood level. The mechanism by which the placenta transports the essential elements, copper and zinc, while limiting the transport of Cd, is unknown (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011).

5.1.3 Excretion

In the absence of kidney damage, the Cd excreted is only a small portion of the total amount of Cd accumulated in the body. The Cd that is filtered by the glomerulus is almost entirely reabsorbed by the proximal tubule epithelial cells; little or no Cd is then excreted in the urine and its half-life may be between 10 and 20 years or even 40 years according to some authors (ANSES 2018).

Cd induced renal damage leads to a dramatic increase in the proportion of excreted Cd in the urine (IUPAC 2018).

For people exposed to Cd almost exclusively from food, the average daily Cd content in faeces is a good indicator of the daily intake, because the major part of the ingested Cd passes through the gastrointestinal tract unabsorbed and reaches the faeces (IUPAC 2018).

Faecal excretion in workers occupationally exposed to Cd reflects mainly Cd dust swallowed from industrial air and/or incidentally ingested from contaminated hands (EFSA, 2009).

Cd accumulates in the mammary gland, with only a small fraction passing over to breastfeeding infant. According to EFSA (2009), concentrations in breast milk are only 5 to 10% of the Cd maternal blood levels (EFSA, 2009).

5.2 Toxicity

Research in adults focuses primarily on kidney and bone effects although results from recent studies also point to increased cancer risks even at low-level environmental exposure.

The relevant toxic endpoints for Cd, detailed below, include carcinogenicity, respiratory toxicity, nephrotoxicity and damage to bone.

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5.2.1 Acute toxicity

Numerous studies have shown that acute inhalation exposure to cadmium can cause severe and potentially lethal lung damage in humans and animals (ATSDR, 2012). Impairment (reversible or not) in pulmonary function has been observed after single acute exposure to high atmospheric concentrations. In one fatal case, the average airborne concentration was estimated to be 8.6 mg.m⁻³ during 5 hours or approximately an 8-hour time-weighted average (TWA) of 5 mg.m⁻³. It has been estimated that an 8-hour exposure to 1 mg/m³ is immediately dangerous for life (SCOEL, 2017).

5.2.2 Chronic toxicity

5.2.2.1 Nephrotoxicity

Nephrotoxic effects generally occur after many years of oral and/or inhalation exposure and result from Cd accumulation in the kidneys (especially in the renal cortex).

Renal damage due to Cd was reported for the first time by Friberg (1948, 1950), in occupationally Cd exposed individuals. Numerous other studies have been published in the meantime. A comprehensive review of workplace studies having measured Cd is available in the ANSES report (2018).

Investigations of Cd-exposed populations have shown that when threshold values of urinary Cd (U-Cd) are exceeded, an increased probability of abnormal values of certain renal function parameters is to be expected. This is caused by dysfunctions and cell damage in certain segments of the nephron. In view of the differences in reaction sensitivity, these effects in the lower concentration range can only be demonstrated in some of the affected individuals who are particularly sensitive (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011).

Renal tubular dysfunction

According to Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011; ANSES, 2018:

Kidney damage results from the accumulation of Cd in cells of the proximal tubules, which causes dose-dependent dysfunction and damage to the tubule cells (Fanconi syndrome).

The earliest currently known sign of incipient renal dysfunction is a reduction in the reabsorption function of the tubule. Low-molecular constituents of the primary urine, which are filtered by glomeruli and are usually largely reabsorbed in the proximal tubules, are subject to increased excretion in the course of disturbed renal function. Characteristic is the appearance in the urine of low molecular weight proteins (LMWPs), as well as markers of cell damage.

“Classical” diagnostic criteria of tubule cell damage include the increased excretion of LMWPs such as alpha-1, beta-2-microglobulin (α 1M and β 2M), retinol-binding protein (RBP) and other low-molecular components of the primary urine (amino acids, glucose, calcium, phosphate). The literature also describes many other biomarkers providing an early indication of tubular cytotoxicity that may be related to Cd exposure (N-acetyl- β -D-glucosaminidase (NAG), α - glutathione S-transferase, 6-keto prostaglandin F1, sialic acid, transferrin and more recently Kim-1 protein being studied in rats).

β 2M and RBP are widely studied proteins for relating urinary concentrations of Cd to the tubular cytotoxicity of Cd in the absence of other renal diseases.

These endpoints permit detection of subtle damage to individual segments of the nephron, but are however not specific to Cd exposure and may be present in various kidney diseases or be caused by other nephrotoxic agents. According to EFSA (2009), urinary RBP is more stable than β 2M at

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the physiological pH of urine and therefore has been proposed as a possible substitute, though it is slightly less sensitive to tubular dysfunction (Bernard and Lauwerys, 1981).

The possible reversibility of Cd induced tubular dysfunction is an important issue to consider for interpretation of the clinical significance of renal biomarkers, e.g. β 2M and RBP (Table 4).

Table 4: Significance of increased values of β 2M and RBP (Bernard et al., 2004)

Urinary β 2M or RBP ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat)	Clinical interpretation
< 300	Normal value
300-1000	Incipient Cd-induced tubular dysfunction (possibility of reversibility if Cd exposure is not too high)
1000-10000	Irreversible tubular proteinuria likely to accelerate the decline of glomerular filtration rate (GFR) with age. At this stage GFR is normal or slightly impaired
>10000	Overt Cd nephropathy usually associated with a decreased GFR

Glomerular effects

Cd is also responsible for glomerular damage. To assess Cd toxicity, measures of renal tubular dysfunction are the most sensitive markers of an adverse effect on the kidneys, because glomerular effects usually occur at higher doses and mild forms of these effects are reversible (IUPAC 2018). However, it is well known that high occupational or environmental exposures to Cd give rise to decreased glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and increased serum creatinine. Often there is a combination with tubular dysfunction, but isolated glomerular dysfunction also occurs (IUPAC 2018).

Despite these limitations, urinary excretion of high molecular weight proteins (HMWPs) and GFR have been respectively used to assess the integrity of glomerular sieve – in terms of retaining HMWPs - and filtration rate or volume of blood undergoing ultrafiltration per unit of time (EFSA 2009). The best markers for glomerular damage are albuminuria and GFR.

For albumin, increases in urine level > 300 mg/day or 200 mg/g creat suggest damage to glomerular structures resulting in overt nephropathy, but values ranging between 20 and 200 mg/g creat could indicate haemodynamic changes associated with incipient glomerulopathy or tubulo-interstitial damage.

Any deviation of GFR from the normal range may indicate renal damage (early stages of certain chronic conditions, e.g. diabetes and lead poisoning). GFR can be assessed measuring the renal clearance of either exogenous or endogenous substances (e.g. creatinine), GFR can also be indirectly assessed measuring serum concentrations of creatinine, LMWPs or cystatin C (EFSA, 2009). However, GFR is rarely measured in clinical practice because of the complexity of the measurement. Recent evidence has suggested that cystatin C may be useful as a marker for glomerular filtration rate (estimated GFR). Indeed, its serum concentration is independent of gender, age, or muscle mass, i.e., typical confounders in assessing GFR (Onopiuk et al., 2015).

Workplace studies on the nephrotoxicity of Cd

Occupational studies provide consistent evidence that Cd targets the kidney after chronic exposure.

Until the 2000s, most field studies carried out on workplaces focused on reporting correlations between urinary Cd concentrations and urinary concentrations of markers of tubular toxicity (β 2M and RBP). The biological reference values for these tubular toxicity markers generally

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corresponded to usual laboratory values, i.e. the 95th percentile of the distribution of these markers concentrations in unexposed controls in occupational studies. Authors then usually calculated the urinary concentrations of Cd from the regression equations. Subsequently, authors have preferred to use the benchmark dose (BMD) approach. This approach consists in identifying the Cd concentration above which 5 to 10% of Cd-exposed workers in a given study are considered have “abnormal”¹⁰ urinary concentrations of tubular toxicity markers. The possible reversibility of Cd induced tubular dysfunction is an important issue to consider for interpretation of the clinical significance of renal biomarkers, e.g. β 2M (Table 4) (ANSES, 2018).

Järup and Elinder (1994) reported abnormal levels of β 2M ($>300 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat) in 10% of the workers with urinary concentrations of Cd over $1.5 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat (when they were more than 60 years old) or $5 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat (when they were less than 60 years old). In 1985, Elinder et al., found β 2M in excess ($> 300 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat) in the urine of 25% of the workers whose urinary Cd level ranged from 2 to $5 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat (ANSES 2018a).

In another occupational study, 10% of workers in the range of $10\text{-}15 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat exceeded the urinary level of 380 and $180 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat for β 2M and RBP, respectively (Jakubowski et al., 1987). At $> 10 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat, not only the urinary excretion of LMWPs was enhanced but also that of albumin and transferrin (Bernard et al., 1990). An age-related decline in maximal GFR was exacerbated in workers with Cd induced microproteinuria at urinary Cd levels of $11.1 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat (Roels et al., 1991).

A summary of results from workplace studies is available in Table 5 (ANSES, 2018).

Table 5: Summary of results from field studies reporting a dose-response relationship between the tubular function parameters and urinary concentrations of Cd

Urinary β 2-microglobulin (β 2M)				
Mode of evaluation	n	Critical value	U-Cd calculated ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat)	Reference
Regression $\log[\text{U-}\beta\text{2M}] (\text{mg.g}^{-1} \text{ creat}) = 1.4 \log[\text{U-Cd}] (\mu\text{g.g}^{-1} \text{ creat}) + \log(0.01)$ (determined graphically) ($r = 0.48$)	58	$0.3 \text{ mg.g}^{-1} \text{ creat}^a$ ($300 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1} \text{ creat}$)	11	Bernard <i>et al.</i> , 1990
Regression $[\text{U-}\beta\text{2M}] (\text{mg.L}^{-1}) = 0.7 \log[\text{U-Cd}] (\text{nmol.L}^{-1}) + 1.1$ ($r = 0.42$)	34			Verschoor <i>et al.</i> , 1987
10% probability of presenting an abnormal proteinuria value	90	$324 \mu\text{g.L}^{-1b}$	11.5	Lauwerys <i>et al.</i> , 1994
BMD ₅ (L ₉₅) for all workers	599	$276 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1} \text{ creat}^c$	9.6 (5.9)	Chaumont <i>et al.</i> , 2011
BMD ₅ (L ₉₅) when excluding smokers			12.2 (5.5)	

¹⁰ The 95th percentile of the concentration of these markers in a group of non-exposed controls is the “normal” reference concentration. Above this, concentrations are then regarded as “abnormal”.

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Urinary β 2-microglobulin (β 2M)				
Mode of evaluation	n	Critical value	U-Cd calculated ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat)	Reference
Logarithmic regression $\log[\text{U}\beta\text{2M}]$ ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}$ creat) = 0.08 [U-Cd] ($\text{nmol}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}$ creat) + $\log(0.008)$ (r = not specified but significant)	60	0.034 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}$ creat ^d (300 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat)	7.8	Elinder <i>et al.</i> , 1985
BMD ₁₀ for workers < 60 years old	561	34 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}$ creat ^e (300 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat)	5	Järup and Elinder, 1994
BMD ₁₀ for workers > 60 years old			1.5	
Urinary retinol binding protein (RBP)				
10 % probability of presenting an abnormal proteinuria value	90	190 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat ^b	10.4	Lauwerys <i>et al.</i> , 1994
BMD ₅ (L ₉₅) for all workers	599	256 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat ^c	5.1 (3)	Chaumont <i>et al.</i> , 2011
BMD ₅ (L ₉₅) when excluding smokers			12.6 (6.6)	

^a on the basis of the upper normal limits routinely used in the laboratory

^b 95th percentile of the distribution in a population of non-occupationally exposed controls (n = 50) in another study (Roels, 1993)

^c 95th percentile of the distribution of concentrations in workers regarded as "subject to low exposure, with urinary Cd concentrations < 1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat" (n = 126 for β 2M and 177 for RBP).

^d 95th percentile of the distribution of concentrations in the population of non-occupationally exposed controls from another study (Buchet *et al.*, 1980)

^e According to the authors, value commonly used in the studies

5.2.2.1.1 Environmental studies on the nephrotoxicity of Cd

The findings of environmental epidemiological studies on the nephrotoxic effects of Cd are summarised in the ATSDR (2012) and EFSA (2009) reports. The lowest observed effect concentrations that point to nephrotoxic effects of Cd are under 1 $\mu\text{g Cd}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat.

The environmental epidemiological studies include a Belgian study on the Cd load of the population, the "Cadmibel study" (Buchet *et al.*, 1990). An increased excretion of LMWP such as β 2M was observed in this study in individuals with urinary Cd concentrations above 2 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat. The threshold values in relation to the increased excretion of NAG, RBP and calcium were even lower. The authors concluded that the threshold for the occurrence of nephrotoxic effects for the general population should be set lower than for industrial workers (see also Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011). Studies have shown that women, children and people with diseases such as diabetes are more vulnerable to renal damage, even at a lower level of exposure (ANSES, 2018). Hotz *et al.* (1999) reported a follow up and found that the urinary levels of Cd were lower in some subjects who previously had displayed increased levels of biomarkers of renal dysfunction, indicating reversibility in some individuals (EFSA, 2009).

Another well-known environmental study, the "OSCAR study", was carried out in Sweden by Järup *et al.* (2000). After adjustment to the mean age of the study population (53 years), the results show an increased prevalence of 10% tubular proteinuria at the urinary Cd concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat (Järup *et al.*, 2000).

From a cross-sectional study with women aged 54-63, Akesson *et al.* (2005) and Suwazono *et al.* (2006) identified a lowest observed effect level (LOEL) and a BMDL₁₀ of 0.8 $\mu\text{g Cd/g creat}$ for α 1M and NAG in urine; and for GFR about 1.2 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat.

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Table 6 gives an overview of environmental studies providing an association between urinary-Cd exposure and tubular effects.

Table 6: Overview of environmental studies (male, female and children) giving an association between urinary Cd and tubular effects (based on EFSA, 2009, for studies published before 2009)

Study	Approach	Sample size (age years)	Criteria	U-Cd critical dose level ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ creat}$)	Comment
Cadmibel (Buchet et al., 1990)	Dose-response Cut-off (Abnormal values): RBP: 338 $\mu\text{g}/24\text{ h}$ NAG: 3.6 IU/24h β2M : 283 $\mu\text{g}/24\text{ h}$	1,699 (20-80 y)	10 % probability of adverse response	β2M : 2 NAG: 1.8 RBP: 1.9	Assuming 1 $\mu\text{g}/24\text{ h} = 0.67\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$.
Oscar (Järup et al., 2000)	Dose-effect, followed by dose-response Cut-off (>95%) α1M : Men: 0.8 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}\text{ creat}$ Women: 0.6 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}\text{ creat}$	470 male (mean age: 54 y); 533 female (mean age: 52 y) (from a possibly polluted area)	10 % excess of LMWP adding to background prevalence of 5 %	α1M : 1	
China I (Jin et al., 2004a)	Dose-response ($\beta\text{2M} > 800\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$)	790, living in two Cd exposed areas and one control area in China	BMD_{05} and BMDL_{05} (5% excess of LMWP over background)	$\text{BMD}_{05}/\text{BMDL}_{05}$ 6.70/5.87 (NAG) 4.46/3.99 (NAG-b) 8.36/7.31 (β2M) 7.98/6.98 (RBP) 15.06/12.18 (ALB)	
China II (Hong et al., 2004)	Dose-response ($\beta\text{2M} > 300\text{ }\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$)	245 (122 from polluted and 123 from non-polluted area)	BMD_{10} and BMDL_{10} (10% excess of LMWP over background)	$\text{BMD}_{10}/\text{BMDL}_{10}$ 1.36/1.13 (β2M) 1.05/0.88 (ALB) 1.48/1.24 (NAG)	Co-exposure to Arsenic
Japan I (Uno et al., 2005)	Dose-response ($\beta\text{2M} > 84\text{th percentile}$: male: 233 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$ female: 274 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$)	410 male (42-57 y); 418 female (41-58 y) Urine sampling 1997-1998	BMD_{05} , BMD_{10} and BMDL_{05} , BMDL_{10}	$\text{BMD}_{10}/\text{BMDL}_{10}$ 1.0/0.7 (β2M) M 0.7/0.6 (NAG) M 1.8/1.3 (β2M) F 1.6/1.2 (NAG) F $\text{BMD}_{05}/\text{LBMD}_{05}$ 0.5/0.4 (β2M) M 0.3/0.3 (NAG) M 0.9/0.7 (β2M) F 0.8/0.6 (NAG) F	

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Study	Approach	Sample size (age years)	Criteria	U-Cd critical dose level ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\cdot\text{creat}$)	Comment
Japan II (Kobayashi et al., 2006)	Dose-response ($\beta 2\text{M}$ >84th percentile: male: 507 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$ female: 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$)	547 male 723 female (≥ 50 y)	BMD_{05} , BMD_{10} and BMDL_{05} BMDL_{05} , BMDL_{10}	$\text{BMD}_{10}/\text{BMDL}_{10}$ 4.6/3.6 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) M 6.4/4.4 (NAG) M 3.3/2.8 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) F 5.6/4.0 (NAG) F $\text{BMD}_{05}/\text{BMDL}_{05}$ 2.6/2.0 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) M 3.6/2.5 (NAG) M 1.9/1.6 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) F 3.1/2.2 (NAG) F	
Japan III (Shimizu et al., 2006)	Dose-response 84 % and 95 % percentile (1mg/g creat) cut-off for $\beta 2\text{M}$	3178 and 294 (≥ 50 y) from polluted and non-polluted areas	BMDL_{05} on dose effect relationship (continuous variables)	84 % cut-off 2.9 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) M 1.5 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) F 95 % cut-off 4.0 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) M 3.6 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) F	
Sweden (Akesson et al., 2005)	Dose-effect (quartiles)	820 female (53-64 y)	LOEL	For NAG and creat clearance in the range 0.65- 0.97 (mean 0.79) or equal to the II quartile For GFR: mean = 1.0, or the III quartile	
Sweden (Suwazono et al., 2006)	Dose-response (hybrid) 95 % of 0 Cd	820 female (53-64 y)	BMD_{05} , BMD_{10} and BMDL_{05} , BMDL_{10}	$\text{BMD}_{10}/\text{BMDL}_{10}$ 1.08/0.83 (NAG) 1.80/1.18 (GFR) $\text{BMD}_{05}/\text{BMDL}_{05}$ 0.64/0.50 (NAG) 1.08/0.70 (GFR)	Unusual approach to BMD calculation (0 Cd ref)
Czech Rep. France Poland (de Burbure et al., 2006)	Dose-effect (quartiles)	804 children (8.5-12 y)	LOEL	RBP: 0.71 NAG: 0.58	Co-exposure to Pb and Hg
Thailand (1 non polluted area and 1 environmentally polluted area) (Nishijo et al., 2014)	Dose-response $\beta 2\text{M}$ men: 2004 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$ women: 1815 $\mu\text{g}/\text{g creat}$ NAG Men: 9.4 IU/g creat Women: 11.2 IU/g creat	40 men and 41 women in a non- polluted area 230 men and 370 women in an environmentally polluted area >40 years	BMD_{05}	Men: 6.9 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) and 4.4 (NAG) Women: 8.1 ($\beta 2\text{M}$) and 6.1 (NAG)	

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Study	Approach	Sample size (age years)	Criteria	U-Cd critical dose level ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ creat}$)	Comment
China (5 Cd polluted areas) (Ke et al., 2015)	Dose response ($\beta\text{2M} > 1000 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ cr}$)	6103 (2715 males and 3388 females) >35 years ($56.4 < \text{Mean} < 62.4$)	BMDL ₁₀	Men: 2 Women: 1.69	
China (non-polluted area) (Wang et al., 2016)	Dose-response Cut-off value (90%): RBP ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ creat}$): Men: 272, Women: 227 β2M ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ creat}$): Men: 780, Women: 690 NAG ($\text{U}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ creat}$): Men: 16.49, Women: 17.82	934 469 men 465 women	BMD ₀₅ , BMD ₁₀ and BMDL ₀₅ , BMDL ₁₀	BMD10/BMDL10 Men: 2.44/1.59 (RBP) Women: 2.43/1.53 (RBP) Men: 2.09/1.24 (B2M) Women: 2.10/1.34 (β2M) Men: 1.8/1.04 (NAG) Women: 2.31/1.37 (NAG) BMD05/BMDL05 Men: 1.69/0.89 (RBP) Women: 1.70/0.76 (RBP) Men: 1.24/0.62 (B2M) Women: 1.35/0.64 (β2M) Men: 0.85/0.49 (NAG) Women: 1.36/0.65 (NAG)	

According to the IUPAC report (2018) and based on the Bernard et al. study (2016), the associations observed between very low-levels of urinary Cd and increases in urinary protein excretion may not be causal. Smoking status and renal physiology also need to be considered. The authors consider that the associations observed at urinary Cd $< 2 \text{ nmol/mmol creat}$ (i.e. $2 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ creat}^{11}$) are likely to have been influenced by these factors (e.g. diuresis) (IUPAC 2018).

5.2.2.2 Effects on bone

Long-term exposure to Cd results in a higher risk of osteoporosis and osteomalacia as a result of changes in the composition of the bone substance. Initial reports of the effects of Cd on bone were from Japan where increased incidences of bone fractures were seen in the course of the “Itai-Itai” disease which is characterised by multiple fractures and distortion of the long bones in the skeleton causing severe pain in the affected individuals (Järup et al., 1998; Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011). The disease exhibits a mixed pattern of osteomalacia and osteoporosis in

¹¹ Conversion factor : $1 \mu\text{mol}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}\text{ creat} = 0,993 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}\text{ creat}$

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combination with kidney damage. Several possible mechanisms have been suggested (Kjellstrom, 1992).

The observed reduction in bone density is accompanied in part by renal dysfunction, leading to an increased elimination of calcium in the urine (Gallagher et al., 2008). Even without tubular dysfunction, environmental epidemiological studies showed the effect of elevated Cd exposure on the demineralisation of bone substance and reactive low parathyroid hormone level and a possible secondary calciuria (Schutte et al., 2008; Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011). Authors have shown a direct effect of Cd on the bones. Akesson et al. (2006) have also reported bone disorders possibly by mechanisms independent of renal disorders, at Cd exposure levels lower than those associated with nephropathy. This work concerned only adult female populations. These results are supported by *in vitro* studies and animal study data (ATSDR, 2012). Nordberg et al. (2007) found evidence to suggest that Cd induced a reduction in gastrointestinal calcium (Ca²⁺) absorption and adversely affected vitamin D hydroxylation as part of a complex influence on bone mineralisation. A Cd-related reactive reduction in parathyroid hormone elimination supports the direct influence of Cd on Ca²⁺ mobilisation from the bones (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011).

The mechanisms for bone effects may be different at high and low Cd exposure. At high exposure with renal tubular damage, the classical mechanisms of renal osteomalacia seem to occur. Loss of calcium and phosphate into urine will result from deficient renal tubular reabsorption. A lowering of serum calcium triggers increased parathyroid activity. Such events, in combination with decreased levels of 1,25 (OH)₂D due to deficient hydroxylation in damaged renal tubular tissue, cause decalcification and changes in bone structure. In long-term low-level Cd exposure there may be non-critical renal tubular dysfunction and normal 1,25(OH)₂D levels but a primary effect on bone tissue occurs, involving increased mobilisation of bone minerals and increased fragility of bones (Nordberg et al., 2015).

In the workplace, some studies reported a relation between urinary Cd and bone toxicity. EFSA (2009) indicated that the Oscar study results (in Sweden) have shown a doubling of the osteoporosis risk at urinary Cd levels of 0.5-3 µg.g⁻¹ creat (Alfven et al., 2000). Based on the Alfven et al., 2000 study, for SCOEL (2017) the U-Cd concentration of 3 µg.g⁻¹ creat could be considered as a threshold for bone effects. In addition, an increased risk of fractures was also noted in the Swedish Oscar study, demonstrating an elevated hazard ratio already at low exposure levels (2-4 µg.g⁻¹ creat) (Alfven et al., 2004).

Several studies dealing with the osteotoxic potential of Cd have been conducted in the general population. These studies have established a probable causal link between Cd exposure and an increased risk of fracture or osteoporosis with statistically significant associations between markers of Cd exposure and effects on bone (IUPAC, 2018). Some of these studies, giving the relation between urinary Cd level and bone effects, are detailed below.

In 2003, Akesson et al. studied bone effects of Cd on 820 women. Median U-Cd was 0.67 µg.g⁻¹ creat. After multivariate adjustment, the authors reported a negative association between bone effects and U-Cd. According to the authors, these results suggested negative effects of low-level Cd exposure on bone, which can be explained by the increase of bone resorption (intensified after menopause).

In 2011 and 2012, Engström et al. conducted two epidemiological studies to investigate a correlation between Cd exposure and decreased bone density (which may increase the risk of osteoporosis or fractures). Both studies involved Swedish women aged 56 to 69 (2,688 individuals). At low levels of urinary Cd (<1.0 µg.g⁻¹ creat), the authors found a relationship

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between prolonged exposure to Cd and a risk of osteoporosis or bone fractures. The urinary Cd concentration corresponding to the lowest observed adverse effect level is $0.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat.

James and Meliker (2013) carried out a pooled analysis based on 7 studies (published after 2004), and showed an association between Cd exposure and occurrence of osteoporosis. A dose-response evaluation (6 studies) suggested increased odds for osteoporosis with increasing Cd levels. However, the authors concluded that inference of causation is ambiguous because of the small number of studies in their review, the cross-sectional designs, and other methodological limitations. Chen et al. (2009) report that in their cohort of 458 individuals bone mineral density continued to deteriorate in high and medium exposed groups after 10 years of lower exposure. These findings show the long-term slow development of this disease and the fact that there seems to be no reversibility (IUPAC, 2018). Chen et al. (2009) found a statistically significant decrease in bone mineral density for a urine Cd concentration $> 5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat in women but no statistically significant associations at lower exposures.

A cohort of 936 Swedish men, aged 70 to 81 years at inclusion (years 2002 to 2004) were followed with periodic bone mineral density and Cd in urine measurements until 2013. All new fractures were registered. Negative associations were observed between U-Cd and bone density, with 4-8 % lower bone density for all sites in the fourth quartile of U-Cd ($0.37\text{-}6.98 \mu\text{g}/\text{g}$ creatinine, mean 0.67), using the first quartile as the reference. In addition, a positive association was also observed between U-Cd in the 4th quartile and incident fractures. (Wallin et al., 2016).

In the IUPAC report (2018), the authors concluded that it is difficult to estimate the lowest exposures giving rise to bone effects. According to the report, it is reasonable to consider that long-term Cd exposures with a level of $5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat or higher is related to an increased risk of adverse bone effects. From $5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat, the association between the level of urinary Cd and bone effects is well established. However, at lower concentration, despite positive results in some studies, this association is not clear and it is currently not possible to be certain that there is a causal relationship between urine Cd in the range $0.5\text{-}5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat and decreased bone mineral density.

Studies showing associations of increased U-Cd concentrations at low levels ($< 5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat) with decreased bone mineral density and/or increased fracture risk generally concerned older people (men and women aged more than 60 and more than 50 years, respectively). Early biological signs of osteoclastic effects (such as increased urine deoxypyridinoline excretion or plasma osteocalcin concentration), but no decreased bone mineral density or increased risk of fractures have been demonstrated at low urine Cd levels ($< 5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat) in younger subjects, including children (Malin-Igra et al., 2019). Concerning the clinical effects on both bone density and the risk of fractures observed at low U-Cd concentrations in older people, one possible explanation is that they result from a direct effect of Cd which would be intensified in older people. An alternative interpretation would be that bone demineralisation in old people could be responsible for a moderate increase of urine Cd concentration, because: a) Cd would be released from the bone pool; b) calciuria and lowering of parathyroid hormone cause an upregulation of calcium and Cd intestinal absorption. It is thus not possible to establish a satisfactory point of departure (POD) for the bone effect.

According to IUPAC report (2018), it is important to have a better understanding of the toxicokinetics of Cd in bone (i.e. tissue levels of Cd that cause decalcification of bone) and the relationship between bone effects and biomarkers of exposure (and additional information is required, such as nutritional factors).

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5.2.2.3 Respiratory effects

Cd compounds cause adverse effects on the respiratory tract through direct action on tissues following deposition of inhaled aerosol. Long-term, i.e. years, of exposure by inhalation may give rise to respiratory disorders including chronic inflammation of the nose, pharynx, and larynx, as well as olfactory disturbances. In the lower airways, chronic obstructive lung disease of varying severity and emphysema are found (IUPAC 2018). Studies were carried out in the workplace on respiratory effects of Cd on workers. The results of these studies show that the observed effects are generally dependent on exposure levels. Jakubowsky et al. (2004) showed a significant decrease in maximum expiratory flow at 50% of forced vital capacity in workers whose cumulative exposure index (CEI) was greater than 4000 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{years}$ (which corresponds to an exposure level of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for 40 years) compared to the group of unexposed workers, and a non-significant decrease in forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV_1) but no decrease in forced vital capacity in particular (or in the other investigated endpoints). Smith et al. (1976) reported a decrease in forced vital capacity in workers exposed to over 200 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (on average) compared to unexposed workers, but did not observe any changes in the other endpoints investigated for respiratory function.

Davison et al. (1988) reported biological changes consistent with emphysema in workers exposed to Cd (alloy manufacturing) compared to unexposed workers (significantly lower capture and pulmonary transfer of carbon monoxide for workers whose CEI was respectively less than 400 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{year}$ and between 400 and 1600 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{year}$). They did not show a decrease in forced vital capacity in these workers.

Based on the observations of respiratory effects in Cd exposed workers (Cortona et al., 1992), SCOEL derived an 8-hours time-weighted average (8-h TWA) value for Cd of 4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ from a LOAEL (12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) based on a moderate increase in residual volume + 7% compared to controls) and which corresponded to 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3\cdot\text{years}$ exposure to Cd (corresponding to 40 years exposure at a level of 12.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) by inhalation (respirable particles) (SCOEL, 2010). In 2017, the experts decided to update this value. Based on evaluations by both WHO (2000) and the German AGS (Ausschuß für Gefahrstoffe; BAuA 2014), it appears that nephrotoxic effects could arise in about 1% of the workforce after 40 years of airborne exposure to 4 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. So the value for the OEL (8h-TWA, not connected with biological monitoring) for Cd and its inorganic compounds has been updated to 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

5.2.2.4 Effect on the cardiovascular system and blood pressure

Cd showed hypertensive effects after long-term administration in the drinking water in animal experiments. However, epidemiological studies have provided contradictory results. Cd appears to play only a minor role – or none at all – with regard to the main risk factors for hypertension (EC, 2007; Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011). EFSA (2009) report that cerebrovascular mortality is possibly associated with high Cd exposure, but the evidence does not suggest that cardiovascular effects are important outcomes at exposure levels that are likely to occur from food.

Moreover, ATSDR reported that the effect of Cd on the cardiovascular system is not an important endpoint, based on workplace studies (ATSDR, 2012). Nordberg et al (2015) reviewing the available evidence noted that decreased blood pressure occurs in persons with severe Cd induced renal injury, but that the issue of blood pressure and mild Cd exposure is still to be resolved.

Quantitative relationships between the Cd concentrations in indicator media such as blood and urine and the degree of mean elevation in blood pressure are not known (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011).

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During the present decade, several epidemiological studies suggest a causal association of Cd exposure in the general population and the risks of several cardiovascular diseases:

- In 2012, a study evaluated the prospective association of blood and urine Cd concentrations with cardiovascular mortality in the US population from the NHANES cohort (1999-2004): 8,989 participants who were more than 20 years were followed for an average of 4.8 years. Hazard ratios for mortality endpoints were estimated, comparing the 80th and 20th percentiles of Cd concentration (0.80 and 0.22 µg/L for blood Cd, and 0.57 and 0.14 µg.g⁻¹ creat for urine cadmium, respectively). The hazard ratios for blood and urine Cd were 1.69 (CI95%: 1.03-2.77) and 1.74 (CI: 1.07-2.83) respectively, for cardiovascular mortality, 1.98 (CI: 1.11-3.54 and 2.53 (CI: 1.54-4.16) for heart disease mortality and 1.73 (CI95%: 0.88-3.40) and 2.09 (CI95%: 1.06-4.13) for coronary heart disease mortality (Tellez-Plaza et al., 2012).
- The same authors obtained similar results in another prospective cohort study of American-Indian adults aged 45-74 years:
 - In 3,348 participants, hazard ratios for mortality endpoints were estimated, comparing the 80th and 20th percentiles of Cd urine concentration (1.62 and 0.55 µg.g⁻¹ creat, respectively). The hazard ratios were 1.43 (CI95%: 1.21-1.70) for cardiovascular mortality, and 1.34 (CI: 1.10-1.63) for coronary heart disease mortality (Tellez-Plaza et al., 2013a).
 - In 2,864 individuals from the same cohort, incident peripheral arterial disease risk associated with Cd exposure was also evaluated. The hazard ratio comparing the 80th and 20th percentiles of Cd urine concentration (1.62 and 0.55 µg.g⁻¹ creat, respectively) was 1.41 (CI95%: 1.05-1.81) (Tellez-Plaza et al., 2013b).
 - Among 3,714 participants in a cross-sectional study, log transformed urinary Cd was significantly associated with higher systolic blood pressure in models adjusted for age, sex, geographic area, body mass index, smoking status and cumulative pack-years, and kidney function. This association persisted in never-smokers but was not significant (Franceschini et al., 2017). These results were corroborated by those from a prospective study in the same cohort. Longitudinal changes in blood pressure across 3 successive study visits (1989-1999) were modelled, using linear mixed models, by baseline log U-Cd(µg.g⁻¹ creat).The estimated changes in diastolic and systolic blood pressure per year were 0.18 mm Hg and 0.62 mm Hg in the highest quintile of urine Cd (1.4-3.6 µg.g⁻¹ creat) . They were -0.11 mm Hg and 0.21 mm Hg in the lowest, respectively. A one unit increase in log-transformed urinary Cd was associated with 10 % greater hypertension risk (CI95%: 1.01-1.20) (Oliver-Williams et al., 2017)
- A pooled analysis of 12 studies published between 2008 and 2013 and evaluating the association between Cd exposure and cardiovascular disease in the general population of the USA, Korea, Japan, Sweden and Belgium showed elevated risks of cardiovascular disease (1.36; CI95%: 1.11-1.66), coronary heart disease (1.30; CI95%: 1.12-1.52), stroke (1.18; CI95%: 0.86-1.59), and peripheral arterial disease (1.49; CI95%: 1.15-1.92). Smoking is both a major cardio-vascular risk and an important determinant of Cd exposure. Eight of the analysed studies estimated risks in never-smokers; seven showed positive associations between Cd exposure and cardiovascular disease risk, but the elevation was

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statistically significant in only 2 of them. The authors concluded that additional prospective studies with long follow-up, repeated individual exposure assessment, standardised cardiovascular outcome, and appropriate account of confounding factors (especially smoking) were required (Tellez-Plaza et al., 2013a).

- A series of studies conducted in a cohort of Swedish men and women from Malmö was recently published:
 - A transversal study examined the association between exposure to Cd as evaluated by a single blood Cd measurement and the prevalence and size of atherosclerotic plaques in the carotid artery in 4,639 middle-aged women and men, in 1991-1994. Comparing quartile 4 with quartile 1 of blood Cd the OR for prevalence of any plaque was 1.3 (1.03-1.8) after adjustment for confounding factors including smoking status. However, it should be noted that no association between blood Cd and atherosclerotic plaques was observed in the never-smoker subgroup (OR: 0.8, when tertile 3 and tertile 1 were compared). According to the authors, these conflicting results may be due to the predominance of dietary sources of Cd in never-smokers, these dietary sources, such as whole grains and vegetables, being also protecting factors for cardiovascular disease (Fagerberg et al., 2015).
 - In a prospective observational study including 4,378 participants during 1992-1994, blood Cd in the 4th quartile (0.5-5.07 µg/L; median: 0.98 µg/L) was associated with incidence of heart failure when compared to the 1st quartile (< 0.15 µg/L ; median: 0.12 µg/L): hazard ratio (HR) was 1.95 (CI95 %: 1.02-3.71) after adjustment for the main confounding factors, including smoking status; in never-smokers, the results were similar but did not attain statistical significance. B-Cd was not associated with risk of incident atrial fibrillation (Borné et al., 2015).
 - In 4,819 individuals (46-67 years) from the cohort, B-Cd was measured in 1991-1994. Incident cardiovascular events were followed until 2010. HR for cardiovascular mortality, stroke, myocardial infarction and acute coronary events were significantly elevated, after adjustment for potential confounders, including smoking, when individuals in the 4th quartile of B-Cd (0.5-5.1 µg/L) were compared to those in the 1st quartile (< 0.17 µg/L). HR in never-smokers were consistent with the adjusted estimates in the whole cohort (Barregard et al., 2016).
 - A case-control study nested in the cohort compared 297 cases of aortic aneurysm and 594 controls matched for age and sex. The highest tertile of B-Cd concentration (> 0.31 µg/L) had a rate ratio of 2.5 (CI 95%: 1.3-5.0) for incident aortic aneurysm when compared to the 1st tertile (< 0.17 µg/L), after adjustment for the main confounders, including smoking status. However B-Cd concentration was not associated with aortic aneurysm risk in never-smokers (OR: 0.5) (Fagerberg et al., 2017).

Globally, the results of the studies published within the last ten years support a causal association of Cd exposure in the general population with the risks of several cardiovascular diseases: coronary heart disease, myocardial infarction, atherosclerotic plaques, stroke, arterial hypertension, heart failure, peripheral arterial disease aortic aneurysm....

However, for each of these diseases the available data are issued from a small number of prospective studies with in most cases a short follow-up. All the potential confounders are not

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appropriately taken into account, especially smoking and also exposure to other metals or metalloids with a more conclusive association with cardiovascular disease. Other limitations of the available data result from the biomonitoring choices: many studies use B-Cd when U-Cd can be regarded as a better measure of long-term exposure, especially in smokers and former smokers; several published prospective studies also used a unique measurement of urine and/or B-Cd for the evaluation of cumulative exposure which may be inappropriate. In the present state of knowledge, cardiovascular endpoints cannot be considered as critical effects of Cd.

5.2.2.5 Diabetes

It is well known that the pancreas is one of the organs in the body with predominant accumulation of Cd. It is also suspected that Cd plays a role in increasing the prevalence of type 2 diabetes, human and animal studies have shown links between Cd exposure and diabetes (Edwards and Prozialek, 2009). The pathogenesis of these effects remains unclear. Prospective studies in general population found no association between diabetes and U-Cd or B-Cd (Borné et al., 2014). Lei *et al.* (2007) reported decreased insulin circulating levels in populations exposed to Cd through contaminated food. This study suggests that these anomalies may occur at exposure levels similar to those causing renal impairment. No field studies on exposure by inhalation have investigated this type of effect. Diabetic subjects with type-2 diabetes are recognised as a group susceptible to Cd exposure because a higher prevalence of tubular dysfunction with respect to Cd in their urine was observed than in non-diabetic subjects (IUPAC, 2018).

5.2.2.6 Neurotoxicity

There is limited evidence of adverse Cd-related effects on the central nervous system (CNS) and peripheral nervous system (PNS) in humans or animals. Ciesielski et al. (2012) studied relationships between neurocognitive test scores and urinary Cd in the NHANES III database from the U.S. general population; they report a statistically significant relationship among never-smokers after multivariable adjustment.

A few studies have found that children's prenatal exposure, assessed by concentrations in the cord blood or in the mothers' urine was associated with cognitive impairments:

- A Chinese study showed an inverse association between the Cd concentration in the cord blood and full scale Intelligence Quotient (IQ) at 4.5 years, after controlling for confounding factors (Tian et al., 2009).
- A study of 1305 Bangladeshi mother-child pairs also found that maternal U-Cd concentrations during pregnancy were inversely associated with children's IQ at 5 years of age (Kippler et al., 2012). The follow-up of these children showed no association at 10 years, but at this time, an inverse association of boys' IQ with their urinary cadmium concentration at the same time was observed (Gustin et al., 2018).
- In a South-Korean mother-child cohort maternal blood cadmium concentration during pregnancy was not associated with neurodevelopment at 6 months (Kim et al., 2013), but it was inversely associated with children's performance IQ at 5 years (Jeong et al., 2015).
- In a Spanish study, no association was observed between urinary cadmium in mothers during the 1st and 3rd trimester of pregnancy, and children's neuropsychological development at the age of 4 years (Forns et al., 2014).
- A study of 574 Cretian mother child pairs showed an inverse association between urinary cadmium in mothers during pregnancy and children's general cognitive score at 4 years of age, but this association was restricted to smokers (Kippler et al., 2016).

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Several studies have also tested an association between children's post-natal cadmium exposure and cognitive performances, with conflicting results (Kippler et al., 2012, Rodriguez-Barranco et al., 2014, Ciesielski et al., 2012, Cao et al., 2009 and Gustin et al., 2018).

Globally, in the present state of knowledge, data on the association of cadmium exposure with neurotoxic effects are still limited and neurological endpoints cannot be considered as critical effects of cadmium.

5.2.2.7 Hepatotoxicity

Even though Cd accumulates in the liver as it does in the kidneys, the studies undertaken in workers exposed to Cd did not show harmful effects on the liver. The liver's resistance to the toxic effects of Cd could be related to its greater capacity to produce MTs, which bind to Cd and are thus believed to lower concentrations of free Cd ions (ATSDR, 2012). No hepatic effects are reported in the general population. For example, in a Japanese study it is reported that among women (age 19-78 years, non-smokers and with non-alcohol consumption), which were highly exposed to cadmium effects on the liver were observed (Ikeda et al., 2000).

5.2.2.8 Carcinogenicity

The carcinogenic effects of Cd compounds were re-assessed by IARC in 2012 (IARC, 2012) and Cd and its compounds were classified as carcinogenic to humans (Group 1). The IARC experts concluded that:

- there was sufficient evidence in humans of the carcinogenicity of Cd and its compounds. Cd and Cd compounds cause cancer of the lung. Also, positive associations have been observed between exposure to Cd and Cd compounds and cancer of the kidney and the prostate.
- there was sufficient evidence in experimental animals of the carcinogenicity of Cd compounds;
- there was limited evidence in experimental animals of the carcinogenicity of Cd metal.

The most convincing relationships between Cd exposure and cancer development are derived from workplace studies and support the conclusion that there is an elevated risk of lung cancer after long-term exposure to high Cd concentrations (in the form of dusts or aerosols that can be inhaled) (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011; ATSDR, 2012). According to IARC (2012), several mechanisms have been identified that potentially contribute to Cd-induced carcinogenesis. Direct binding to DNA appears to be of minor importance and evidence for mutagenicity is weak. Convincing evidence exists on disturbances of DNA-repair and tumour-suppressor proteins, which lead to chromosomal damage and genomic instability. Further reported effects include changes in DNA-methylation patterns as well as interactions with signal-transduction processes, which may contribute to the deregulation of cell growth. However, it is not yet possible to assess the relative contributions of these latter mechanisms for cancer in humans.

According to SCOEL (2017), several mechanisms have been identified, none of them stochastic. Cd can therefore be considered as a Category C carcinogen, i.e. a genotoxic carcinogen for which a practical threshold can be identified. In consequence, a set of OELs (8h-TWA and BLV) will be protective that avoids toxicity in workers at the relevant targets for carcinogenicity, i.e. locally at the airways and systemically at the kidneys.

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5.2.2.9 Reproductive toxicity

Although Cd was studied with regard to possible reproductive toxicity on many occasions, the contribution of this toxicant is generally uncertain due to the presence of a variety of exposures that may have contributed to adverse reproductive outcomes such as preterm delivery or low birth weight (EFSA, 2009). According to the ATSDR report, the evidence is insufficient to determine an association between inhalation exposure to Cd and reproductive effects (ATSDR, 2012).

According to IUPAC (2018), several animal studies showed necrosis within the testes after injection of Cd salts in doses of one or a few mg.kg⁻¹ bw; while testicular necrosis occurs after a single injection of Cd salts, such effects do not occur if the dose is fractioned or given over a longer period of time as in humans under occupational or environmental circumstances. Exposure to Cd can cause changes in the levels of male sex hormones.

In 2004, Zeng et al. reported changes in the levels of male reproductive hormones in a population exposed to Cd. Results from epidemiological studies on the effect of Cd on birth weight are inconclusive. Studies carried out on female animals showed that relatively high doses of Cd can cause changes in the ovaries, changes in ovarian hormonal production and placenta necrosis (IUPAC, 2018).

One study linked delayed psychomotor development at the age of 6 years to elevated Cd concentrations in hair collected at birth (Bonithon-Kopp et al., 1986). ATSDR (2012) reported that in utero inhalation exposure to cadmium oxide (0.16 mg Cd.m⁻³) resulted in significant decreases in pup viability, foetal body weight, pup body weight gain, delayed ossification, and impaired performance on neurobehavioral tests. The possible developmental neurotoxicity of Cd at low exposure levels is addressed above (see 3.2.2.6 Neurotoxicity).

5.2.2.10 Endocrine effects

For cadmium, the reproductive system is the most sensitive system. The effects on the reproductive system are described above. In 2012, ATSDR reports effects on pancreas, growth hormones, thyroid... Despite these results, endocrine effects of Cd exposure are not dealt in this report because of a lack of data.

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6 HBM parameters

6.1 Choice of biomarkers of exposure

Cd levels in blood, urine, faeces, liver, kidney, hair, and other tissues are widely used as indicators of exposure to Cd. In the general population or in workers, Cd exposure is commonly monitored through either blood or urine Cd concentrations.

6.1.1 Cadmium in blood

In blood, Cd is mainly found in erythrocytes. Plasma Cd concentrations are low. Whole B-Cd is considered the most valid marker of recent exposure (3-6 months) and is usually assessed.

Cadmium concentration in blood increases linearly up to 120 days and then levels off (Lauwerys et al., 1979).

Cd in blood partially reflects the accumulated body burden over recent weeks and months. However, when exposure changes, it is the indicator that reacts most rapidly. As such, it partly reflects the rate of change in the Cd body burden and can be used to verify that exposure to Cd is adequately controlled in the short term. It can therefore be used as a biomarker of exposure as part of medical monitoring for controlling exposure in the workplace (taking into account all sources of exposure, including oral, which is often non-negligible in the case of metals) (ANSES, 2018). Moreover, there is a high correlation between U-Cd and B-Cd (Akerstrom et al., 2013). According to EFSA (2009), both biomarkers (U-Cd and B-Cd) are equally good estimates of Cd body burden in environmentally exposed populations except when dietary Cd exposure changes.

B-Cd has advantages over U-Cd as it is not subject to confounding by diuresis and co-excretion of proteins. However, B-Cd may be more directly influenced by effects related to the influence of Cd on the vascular system than U-Cd (IUPAC, 2018). The biological half-life of B-Cd has also a slow component with a half-life of 7-16 years (IUPAC, 2018).

6.1.2 Cadmium in urine

Urinary Cd is considered the best biomarker of long-term exposure to Cd (and the most extensively studied biomarker of cumulative body burden of Cd).

In healthy kidneys urinary Cd is proportional to the concentration in the renal cortex (urinary Cd of $5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat roughly corresponds to $100 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ in the renal cortex). Numerous publications show that there is a correlation between urinary Cd and elevated urinary concentrations of some biomarkers in the early stage of renal impairment. The presence of Cd and the Cd-MT complex in urine is generally considered to result from natural turnover of proximal tubule epithelial cells. As described above, Cd is not predominantly excreted in the urine. Only once the Cd body load becomes high enough or kidney damage begins to manifest, the urinary excretion of Cd increases significantly (Prozialeck and Edwards, 2010). However, in general, there is a relationship between the level of cumulative Cd exposure (from data mainly on ingestion) and urinary Cd concentrations (Kido et al., 2004; Kobayashi et al., 2005; Shimbo et al., 2000).

One of the most important factors affecting urinary Cd is diuresis. The concentration of Cd in urine shows a strong positive correlation with the concentration of creatinine in urine, which makes it necessary to adjust for the hydration status via either creatinine or specific gravity. Creatinine adjustment of U-Cd is however not perfect since it leaves a residual dependence on urine flow. This dependence can lead to confounding, with false positive association between U-Cd/g creatinine and the concentration in urine of proteins such as β 2M and RBP (IUPAC, 2018).

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According to IUPAC (2018), the co-excretion phenomenon between Cd and LMWPs is an important source of confounding in epidemiology, as it may generate associations mimicking those induced by Cd toxicity (while it reflects the intra-individual variability in the renal handling of proteins). Some of the associations between low U-Cd and urine LMWPs in adult or child general populations are likely a result of such confounding.

6.1.3 Conclusion

Urinary Cd is a well-known and reliable indicator of long-term exposure to Cd. It is the most studied and used biomarker of Cd-exposure. In conclusion it is the most reliable biomarker of Cd-exposure for the general population as well as for occupationally exposed adults.

B-Cd is a useful indicator of Cd-exposure during the last months (3-6 months). Whereas, after accumulation of Cd, the blood level is dependent on the body burden. Therefore, it is a useful biomarker to monitor Cd occupational exposure, especially for new employees at the workplace. Therefore, B-Cd can also be recommended as a biomarker of exposure for workers in addition to U-urinary Cd.

6.2 Choice of biomarkers of effect

Cd nephrotoxicity has long been known and is generally used as the basis for determining biological values, because it is the best-characterised effect resulting from chronic exposure to Cd (see chapter 3.2.2). A review by Prozialeck and Edwards (2010) described the mechanisms of Cd nephrotoxicity and the associated biomarkers are reported in the literature. During chronic exposure to Cd the kidney is indeed a target organ of Cd toxicity.

As described above (Chapter 3.2.2.1) for glomerular kidney effects, useful biomarkers of effects are the GFR and albumin in urine and for tubular effects, the most sensitive biomarkers are RBP, β 2M, α 1M, NAG.

β 2M is a widely studied protein for relating urinary concentrations of Cd to the tubular cytotoxicity of Cd in the absence of renal disease. However, its lack of stability in acidic urine could result in false results and underestimation of the actual excretion. α 1M protein is another LMWP that can be measured in urine for detection of tubular dysfunctions.

The literature describes many other biomarkers providing an early indication of tubular cytotoxicity that may be related to Cd exposure, as NAG, α -glutathione S-transferase, 6-keto prostaglandin F₁, sialic acid, transferrin and more recently Kim-1 protein (ANSES, 2018).

The data that can be used to relate urinary Cd concentrations to biomarkers of renal effects are limited. As a result, only β 2M and RBP were selected as possible biomarkers of effect.

6.3 Analytical methods

The use of mass spectrometry after excitation in inductively coupled plasma (ICP-MS) is recommended for the determination of Cd concentrations in blood and urine of individuals with low Cd exposure. For very low concentrations (close to the limit of detection), an analytical uncertainty of 20% has to be included in the assessment (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011).

The deliverable D9.2 "Prioritised list of biomarkers, matrices and analytical methods for the 1st prioritisation round of substances"¹² produced within HBM4EU also concludes that "the most sensitive technique for the determination of Cd in blood and urine is ICP-MS. However, for the urinary levels of Cd, correction measures must be taken for the interferences of tin and

¹² Available at : <https://www.hbm4eu.eu/deliverables/>

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molybdenum oxide during the analysis, especially at low levels. Therefore, the most suitable technique would be inductively coupled plasma dynamic reaction cell mass spectrometry (ICPDRC-MS), which reduces drastically the molybdenum-based polyatomic interferences. Alternative analytical methodologies able to overcome the inherent problems of the interferences should be explored". A promising technique is ICP-MS/MS which allows an interference-free determination of Cd by oxidising MoO⁺ to MoO₂⁺ (Bolea-Fernandez, 2017). Further investigations are needed to evaluate ICP-MS/MS for Human Biomonitoring of Cd. β₂M can be measured in urine using an enzyme immunoassay (Kawada et al., 1990; Chaumont et al., 2011), by radioimmunoassay (Roels et al., 1978), by simple immunodiffusion test (Garçon et al., 2004 and 2007) or by immunonephelometry (Bernard et al., 1981). RBP can be measured in urine by simple immunodiffusion test (Nogawa et al., 1979), by the automated immunonephelometry technique (Roels et al., 1978) or using the enzyme immunoassay (Garçon et al., 2004 and 2007; Chaumont et al., 2011).

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7 Derivation of HBM-GVs for cadmium

The existing database on biomonitoring data on Cd allows for the derivation of HBM-GVs for the general population and for workers based on a relationship between human internal concentrations and health effects. Various EU/international bodies have already derived such values. An overview of the existing values is presented below.

7.1 Overview of existing internal toxicity reference values

7.1.1 General population

Table 7: Existing internal toxicity reference values or critical values for the general population

Agency or committee(year)	Endpoint	Key study	Point of departure	Assessment factors	Critical value
EFSA (2009)	Renal tubular dysfunction based on increased β 2M concentration (morning urine sample)	Meta-analysis of 35 studies (described in EFSA, 2009)	BMD ₅ L ₉₅ : 4 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat	A chemical-specific adjustment factor of 3.9, to account for inter-individual variation	1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat
UBA (2011)	Renal tubular dysfunction	Based on EFSA 2009			HBM-I adults: 1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat HBM-I children (3-14y): 0.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat
ATSDR, 2012	Renal tubular dysfunction (excess risk of low molecular weight proteinuria - β 2M or α 1M)	Meta-analysis based on 7 studies (ATSDR, 2012)	BMD ₁₀ L ₉₅ : 0.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat	none	0.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat
ANSES, 2019	Bone effects	Engstrom et al. (2011, 2012)	NOAEL: 0.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat	none	0.5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat
IUPAC, 2018	Renal tubular dysfunction (excess risk of low molecular weight proteinuria - β 2M or α 1M)	Jin et al., 2004; Bernard et al., 1994 Buchet et al., 1990 Olsson et al., 2002 Suwazono et al., 2006	LOAEL 2 nmol.mmol ⁻¹ <i>No NOAEL can be derived because of uncertainties concerning occurrence of low molecular weight proteinuria at U-Cd less than 2 nmol.mmol⁻¹</i>		

EFSA panel used the threshold value of U-Cd (1 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat.) to establish a tolerable weekly intake (TWI) for Cd of 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw (EFSA, 2009). From the same data as EFSA (2009), the JECFA (Joint FAO/WHO Expert Committee on Food Additives) established in 2010 a provisional tolerable monthly intake (PTMI) of 25 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw.

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ATDSR derived a minimal risk level (MRL) of 0.01 $\mu\text{g Cd.m}^{-3}$ for chronic-duration inhalation exposure (≥ 1 year) to Cd using the U-Cd level of 0.5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat as the point of departure.

7.1.2 Occupationally exposed adults

Table 8: Occupational biological limit values for U-Cd

Agency or committee - country	Endpoint	Key study	Point of departure	Assessment factors	Critical value
SCOEL (2017)	Renal tubular dysfunction (excess risk of low molecular weight proteinuria - $\beta 2\text{M}$ or $\alpha 1\text{M}$)	Buchet et al., 1990; Hotz et al., 1999; Järup et al., 2000 Noonan et al., 2002 Jin et al., 2002) (general population)	LOAEL : 2 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat <i>SCOEL mentioned a LOAEL identified for renal effects from studies at workplace about 5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat</i>	None	BLV ¹³ : 2 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat
ANSES (2018)	Renal tubular dysfunction (excess risk of low molecular weight proteinuria - $\beta 2\text{M}$ and RBP)	Chaumont et al. 2011 (workers)	BMD _{10L95} : 5.5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat	None	BLV: 5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat
		Järup and Elinder 1994 (workers)	BMD ₁₀ : 1.5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat	None	Threshold value for initiating monitoring of renal function biomarkers 2 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat
INSST ¹⁴ (2017)	Bases on SCOEL value				VLB ¹⁵ : 2 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat
ACGIH (2016) - USA	Renal tubular dysfunction (excess risk of LMW proteinuria - $\beta 2\text{M}$, NAG or others)	Occupational studies (e.g. Chaumont et al. 2011)	BEI ¹⁶ : 5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat <i>According to ACGIH panel, studies showed increase of NAG or $\beta 2\text{M}$ at U-Cd level of 5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat. Although the data suggested that the changes might progress and become clinically significant when combined with effects associated with aging. So it was prudent to maintain U-Cd concentration below 5 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat</i>		
FIOH (2014) - Finland					BAL ¹⁷ : 20 nmol.L ⁻¹ (2.2 $\mu\text{g/L}$)

¹³ Biological Limit Value

¹⁴ <https://www.insst.es/documents/94886/431980/DLEP+B+1++Cadmio+y+compuestos+inorg%C3%A1nicos++A%C3%B1o+2018.pdf/aa6ab41c-88e5-4564-99cb-b3c8aac3ff7c?version=1.0>, consulted on 30 August 2019

¹⁵ Valores Límite Biológicos (BLV)

¹⁶ Biological Exposure Index

¹⁷ Biological Action Level

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Table 9: Occupational biological limit values for B-Cd

Agency or committee - country	Endpoint	Key study	Point of departure	Assessment factors	Critical value
ANSES (2018) - France	Renal dysfunction (excess risk of LMW proteinuria - β 2M, RBP, NAG-reduced glomerular filtration) and correlation between U-Cd and B-Cd	Several occupational studies	4 $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$		BLV: 4 $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$
INSST (2017) - Spain	Based on the ACGIH 2016 value				5 $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$
ACGIH (2016) - USA	Renal dysfunction (excess risk of LMW proteinuria - β 2M)	Järup et al., 1988	5%, 10% and 16% prevalence of tubular proteinuria appeared at B-Cd concentrations of 2.8, 5.6 and 10 $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$ The prevalence of tubular proteinuria may become significant even if B-Cd remain for many years below 5 $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$	None	5 $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$
FIOH (2007) - Finland					50 nmol.L^{-1} (5.6 $\mu\text{g/L}$)

The MAK commission recommended in 2011 (MAK, 2011) only BAR¹⁸ values for non-smokers (U-Cd: 0.8 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat and B-Cd: 1 $\mu\text{g.L}^{-1}$)

7.2 Choice of the critical effect

Nephrotoxicity appears as the most sensitive endpoint for which the database supplied information on a quantitative relation between concentrations of biomarkers and effects. As a result, the renal effect was chosen for establishing HBM-GVs for Cd.

Whereas there is sufficient evidence that Cd and Cd compounds are carcinogenic to humans (classification as carcinogenic to humans, group 1) (see chapter 3.2.2.8), it is not possible to establish one or more HBM-GVs on the basis of Cd's carcinogenicity because of the lack of consistent relationship in epidemiological studies and the complex interactions with smoking and other competing or co-carcinogenic factors discussed. In any case, it does not seem possible to

¹⁸ For substances for which the concept of health-based threshold values is not applicable "Biologische Arbeitsstoff-Referenzwerte" (BARs, Biological Reference Values for Chemical Compounds in the Work Area) represents the upper reference concentration of a biomarker in the general adult population without occupational exposure to the agent. In general, a BAR corresponds to the 95th percentile of the sample distribution

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properly assess the dose-response relationship given that co-exposure to other carcinogens cannot be ruled out.

The literature data indicate a potential causal link between long-term exposure to Cd and bone toxicity. However, the epidemiological findings on bone effects do not allow the identification of critical blood or urine Cd concentrations (see chapter 3.2.2.2): at low urine Cd levels ($< 5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat) a positive association between biomarker and decreased bone mineral density or risk of fractures has been inconsistently observed. When bone effects were associated with Cd levels increases, it was generally only in older people (> 50 years or > 60 years) and often only in women. In several studies from Sweden (Engström et al., 2011 and 2012), a positive association between U-Cd concentrations and bone demineralisation and risk of fractures was shown, but it cannot be excluded that the meaning of this association was that bone demineralisation due to older age increased U-Cd levels through liberation of bone Cd and upregulation of both calcium and Cd intestinal absorption (both elements are sharing the same intestinal transporter). Concerning respiratory effects, these effects are well established as a result of excessive exposures to Cd compounds in the past at the workplace. According to IUPAC (2018), there is limited evidence concerning effects on lung function and it is difficult to discriminate between effects related to Cd exposure and to toxic effects of cigarette smoke.

7.3 Derivation of a HBM-GV_{GenPop}

7.3.1 Choice of the key study

Despite more recent studies conducted on renal effects, the EFSA meta-analysis (EFSA, 2009) is selected as the key study in the present report. The EFSA Scientific Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain (CONTAM) carefully evaluated the arguments for and against different markers and their interpretations for the onset of renal dysfunction; the meta-analysis is based on 35 studies, described in the technical report.

To determine an effect threshold, the CONTAM panel carried out a meta-analysis of the studies published up to 2008 in which associations between urinary Cd (as an indicator of cumulative Cd exposure) and $\beta 2\text{M}$ as an indicator of early nephrotoxic effects were examined. The objective of this meta-analysis was the derivation of a benchmark dose and its 95% confidence lower bound (BMDL_{95}) for humans, using cut off points relevant to clinical changes in the target organ. Adopting the estimations of Bernard (2008) as a basis, the panel decided to perform BMD modelling only with the studies using $\beta 2\text{M}$ as the biomarker of renal effects. The CONTAM panel calculated a substance-specific adjusted benchmark concentration, which is suitable to prevent an excretion of $\beta 2\text{M}$ that is elevated by 5% and selecting the 95% lower confidence limit for this value ($\text{BMD}_{5\text{L}95}$). The 35 studies in which $\beta 2\text{M}$ was used as a biomarker for renal damage included 30,000 subjects (Caucasians and Asians). The EFSA Panel applied adjustment to take into account variability due to ethnicity; in Caucasian studies, the authors adjusted for urinary pH (degradation of $\beta 2\text{M}$ in acidic urine).

7.3.2 Choice of the POD

The EFSA panel evaluated the dose-response relationship and chose three different cut-off values of $\beta 2\text{M}$ to derive BMD and BMDL in a hybrid approach:

- One statistically-based cut-off value: the 95th percentile (P95) of $\beta 2\text{M}$ at background urinary Cd concentrations
- Two biologically-based cut-off values: 300 μg and 1000 μg $\beta 2\text{M}$ (see also table 4)

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Cut-off limits for extra risk of 5% (BMD₅ and BMDL₅) were selected and calculated for the total population and for the subpopulation of non-occupationally exposed subjects with a mean age greater than 50 years (Table 10).

Table 10: BMD and BMDL estimates by EFSA (2009) for various cut-off values for β 2M leading to an extra-risk of 5% in the total population and non-occupationally exposed population over 50 years of age adjusted to Caucasian ethnicity

	Statistical cut-off value for β 2M ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat)		β 2M > 300 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat	
	BMD5	BMDL5	BMD5	BMDL5
U-Cd ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat) from the whole population	3.98	3.62	4.65	3.84
U-Cd ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat) from non-occupationally exposed subjects over 50 years	5.28	4.89	5.25	4.45

As described by the CONTAM panel, the selected POD is based on an overall group-based BMDL₅ of **4 μg urinary Cd.g⁻¹ creat** (range of BMDL5 for the statistical cut-off and biological cut-off value of 300 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat).

7.3.3 Assessment factor and resulting HBM-GV_{GenPop}

EFSA further adopted a chemical-specific adjustment factor¹⁹ of 3.9, which may be viewed as an assessment factor (AF) for intra-species variability, so that the inter-individual variance in sensitivity to Cd can be taken into consideration to an appropriate degree and to also protect groups of people who are sensitive. As a result a value of 1 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat has been derived which can be regarded as HBM-GV_{GenPop} for adults over 50 years of age:

$$\text{HBM-GV}_{\text{GenPop}} (\text{adults over 50 years}) = 1 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1} \text{ creat}$$

The CONTAM panel added that the reference point is consistent with earlier calculations in individual studies using other biomarkers of kidney and bone effects.

According to EFSA (2009), these results are also supported by a study carried out in workers (Elinder et al., 1985). Based on this study (60 workers, 58 males and 2 females), the EFSA panel calculated a value of 1 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat (applying an AF for inter-individual variability of 3 to take into account the “healthy workers effect”).

Cd accumulates in the human body throughout life. Therefore, it seems appropriate to propose biological threshold values according to age.

PBPK modelling was used (see Annex 10.1) to estimate, at constant Cd intake (i.e. 0.72 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ bw/d), limit or so-called ‘alert’ values of urinary Cd according to age leading to the HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 1 μg Cd.g⁻¹ creat at age 55-60 years (concentrations are predicted to reach a peak at age 55 years (ATSDR, 2012)) (table 11).

¹⁹ Equivalent to the 95th percentile (BMD) / Median (BMD)

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Table 11: U-Cd (median) alert levels for age ranges (with indicative median body-weight considered for the age ranges)

Age (years)	Body weight median (kg)	U-Cd median (min-max) ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat)	U-Cd threshold values ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat)
=<10	23.8	0.1 (0.03-0.14)	0.1
11-20	52.8	0.18 (0.15-0.23)	0.2
21-30	67.3	0.29 (0.24-0.36)	0.3
31-40	72.4	0.5 (0.39-0.63)	0.5
41-50	72	0.8 (0.67-0.93)	0.8
>50	60	0.99 (0.95-1.00)	1

This differentiation according to age represents a further specification and advancement of the HBM-I values proposed earlier by the German HBM-Commission (2011) (adults: $1 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat, children $0.5 \mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat).

7.4 Derivation of HBM-GV_{Worker}

7.4.1 Urinary Cd

7.4.1.1 Choice of key study

Despite the strength of the EFSA (2009) meta-analysis described above, it may not be appropriate to use the results for workers since the EFSA target population was mostly the general population (the data were provided by a very heterogeneous population of which only 1% were workers (ANSES, 2018)).

The study by Chaumont et al., in 2011 is the only one providing a robust calculation of a BMD (and the calculation of uncertainty) in a large population ($n = 599$) of French, European and American **workers** employed in 4 nickel-Cd battery plants for 18.8 years on average, using urinary $\beta 2\text{M}$ and RBP as biomarkers of effect. This study has certain methodological advantages, such as the separate analysis of smokers from the studied group.

7.4.1.2 Choice of POD and resulting HBM-GV_{Worker}

The Chaumont et al. (2011) study reported urinary Cd levels corresponding to elevated urinary RBP and $\beta 2\text{M}$ concentrations for 5% of workers (BMD_5) and calculated the associated concentrations of Cd (Table 12).

Table 12: BMD₅ and BMD_{5L95} corresponding to abnormal levels of LMWPs in urine

Urinary biomarker with abnormal values		Urinary concentration of Cd ($\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat)	
		With smokers	Without smokers
$\beta 2\text{M}$	BMD ₅	5.1	12.6
	BMD _{5L95}	3	6.6
RBP	BMD ₅	9.6	12.2
	BMD _{5L95}	5.9	5.5

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The lowest $BMD_{5L_{95}}$, in the non-smoker subgroup (i.e. $5.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat) is considered as the POD. Indeed, one strength of the study relies on the exclusion of smokers; also urinary concentrations are not influenced by tobacco. The value of $5.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat is considered as the POD on the basis of an increase in the prevalence of abnormal urinary concentrations of RBP ($BMD_{5L_{95}}$: $5.5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat) or $\beta_2\text{M}$ ($BMD_{5L_{95}}$: $6.6 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat) (ANSES, 2018).

As the average age of workers in the study by Chaumont et al. (2011) was 45 years (± 10 years), using this study to establish a $HBM-GV_{\text{Worker}}$ could mean that this value offers less protection to workers with a longer exposure. It would be prudent to apply a safety factor. Therefore, an assessment factor for intraspecies differences (AF_H) of 3 can be applied by default.

$HBM-GV_{\text{Worker}} = 1.83 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat rounded to $2 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat

In 2017, SCOEL recommended a value of $2 \mu\text{g Cd}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat, based on environmental studies (Buchet et al., 1990; Hotz et al., 1999; Järup et al., 2000, Noonan et al., 2002, Jin et al., 2002) because the European committee estimated that the threshold level observed from occupational studies (i.e. $5 \mu\text{g Cd/g}$ creatinine) does not offer protection for workers who may suffer from renal disease during or, most often, after their occupational career (and considering the long half-life of Cd in humans and its accumulation with age). Therefore SCOEL recommended a BLV of $2 \mu\text{g Cd}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat which is consistent with $HBM-GV_{\text{Worker}}$.

7.4.2 Blood Cd

As described in chapter 4.1.3, B-Cd can be recommended as a biomarker of exposure, in addition to U-Cd, for workers and especially for new employees or when the intensity of cadmium exposure is rapidly variable.

At the workplace, several studies report correlations between blood and urinary Cd but also between B-Cd and markers of renal toxicity (i.e. RBP and $\beta_2\text{M}$). These studies are described in annex 10.4.

In 2016, ACGIH recommended a BEI of $5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The committee maintains the previous recommendation based on additional data (e.g. Järup *et al.* (1988) study). Indeed Järup et al. showed a dose-relationship between prevalence of tubular proteinuria ($\beta_2\text{M} > 311 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat.) and B-Cd on workers exposed to Cd oxide dust in battery manufacturing. A prevalence of 10% appeared at concentrations of B-Cd at $5.6 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$.

Based on ACGIH recommendation (2016), a **$HBM-GV_{\text{Worker}}$ for Cd in whole blood of $5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$** can be recommended.

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8 Level of confidence attributed to the derived HBM-GVs

As mentioned in the HBM4EU concept document to derive HBM-GVs, it is suggested to attribute a level of confidence (low, medium or high) to each calculated HBM-GV. The level of confidence should reflect the uncertainties identified during the elaboration of the value and could constitute a good incentive to later revise values with an estimated 'lower' level of confidence.

However, it should be specified that the levels of confidence proposed in this document are not determined according to an established recognised methodology, but rather rely on expert judgment regarding the reliability of the data and the calculation method used to derive the HBM guidance values.

The levels of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV for the general population are set to 'high'. Please refer to the n°2 note of the factsheet for explanation on this level of confidence estimate.

The level of confidence attributed to the HBM-GV for the working population is also set to "high/medium". Please, refer to the n°2 note of the factsheet presented for explanation on this level of confidence appreciation.

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9 Discussion

In the present report, for evaluating internal exposure to Cd compounds of the general population as well as of workers it is recommended to determine Cd in urine. U-Cd is well related to renal effects in both the general population and workers.

The HBM-GV_{GenPop} of 1 µg.g⁻¹ creat for adults over 50 years is the result of a meta-analysis performed by EFSA and further adjusted with a well-founded assessment factor (EFSA, 2009). A weakness of this meta-analysis is the fact that several studies of high quality were excluded (due to either the sampling modality or to the use of other renal markers of toxicity than β2M). On the other hand, the CONTAM panel confirmed that the reference point is consistent with earlier calculations in individual studies using other biomarkers of kidney and bone effects. At a value below 1 µg Cd.g⁻¹ creat in urine there is only a slight risk of increased β2M excretion, even for sensitive individuals (at the age of 50 or older). In order to maintain the desired level of protection, lower levels for younger ones were derived here. Exceedence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} given under 5.3.3 indicates a long-term considerably increased burden of Cadmium, which might lead to the occurrence of renal dysfunction in old age if exposure continues. The goal of selecting this sensitive HBM-GV is to discover the onset of pathological changes as early as possible and allow for exposure minimisation. A possible reversibility must be considered against the background of the long half-life of cadmium (Kommission Human-Biomonitoring, 2011).

The HBM-GV_{Worker} of 2 µg.g⁻¹ creat is based on the study of Chaumont et al., 2010, which provides a robust calculation of a BMD (and the calculation of uncertainty) in a large population of workers (n = 599) classified according to their smoking status. The difference in the HBM-GV values between workers and the general population is explained by the “healthy workers effect”. Indeed, the renal damage observed in the general population at low level Cd exposure can be due to pre-existing renal diseases (e.g. renal complications of diabetes). Workers occupationally exposed to Cd are considered healthy (and a homogeneous population) and should not be exposed to Cd if they suffer from such diseases. In 2010 and 2017, SCOEL recommended the same value for workers based on general population studies (2 µg.g⁻¹ creat.) considering that workers may suffer from such diseases during or most often after their occupational career.

For workers it can be useful to control exposure to Cd by monitoring B-Cd, indeed it is the indicator that responds the fastest. As such, it partly reflects the rate of change in the Cd body burden and can be used to verify that exposure to Cd is adequately controlled in the short term. The B-Cd HBM-GV_{Worker} is set to 5 µg.L⁻¹ based on the ACGIH recommendation and this monitoring is recommended in addition to U-Cd.

Cadmium concentrations, especially in the blood, are influenced by tobacco consumption and to a lesser extent by diet. For workers, to simplify the monitoring procedures, all urine specimens can be taken in the morning before starting the shift (this avoids the risk of external contamination of samples), regardless of the day of the working week.

Observed associations between urinary Cd excretion from 0.5 µg.g⁻¹ creat upwards and bone demineralisation and/or cardiovascular effects must be clarified by further investigations.

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Currently there is sufficient evidence that Cd and Cd compounds are carcinogenic to humans (group 1), but it is not possible to establish one or more HBM-GVs on the basis of cadmium's carcinogenicity due to the lack of a consistent relationship in epidemiological studies and the complex interactions with smoking and other competing or co-carcinogenic factors discussed. In 2017, SCOEL considered Cd as a Category C carcinogen, i.e. a genotoxic carcinogen for which a mode of action-based threshold can be identified. Therefore, according to SCOEL a set of OEL (8h-OEL and BLV) will be protective that avoids toxicity in workers at the relevant targets for carcinogenicity (locally at the airways and systematically at the kidneys).

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10 Factsheets

10.1 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for the general population

Compound: Cd			
Target population : general population			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV_{GenPop} and Status			
Target population: general population			
HBM-GV_{SGenPop}	1	Age (years)	U-Cd (µg.g-1 creat)
		=<10	0.1
		11-20	0.2
		21-30	0.3
		31-40	0.5
		41-50	0.8
>50	1		
Level of confidence	2	Assumed to be high	See note for explanation
HBM-GV_{GenPop} status	3	Preliminary	
HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5		
EC-Nr.	6	231-152-8	
CAS-Nr.	7	7440-43-9	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Carc. Cat. 1B (H350) Mut.2 (H341) Repr.1B (H361fd)	
Molar mass	9	112.41	Cd
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Urinary Cd	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	Cd = 112.41 g/mol	
Derivation method and calculation			
Derivation method	17	Based on a relation between health effects and biomarker concentration	
Key study, Author(s), Year	18	EFSA, 2009	
Species	18	Human	
Route/type of study	18	Meta-analysis	

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Critical endpoint	18	Nephrotoxicity															
POD value	18	BMD ₅ L ₉₅ Benchmark concentration, which is suitable to prevent an excretion of β ₂ M that is elevated by 5% and selecting the 95% lower confidence limit for this value: 4 µg.g ⁻¹ creat of urinary Cd (range of BMDL ₅ for the statistical cut-off and biological cut-off value limit of 300 µg.g ⁻¹ creat)															
Assessment factor	19	3.9															
Calculated HBM-GV _{GenPop}	20	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Age (years)</th> <th>U-Cd (µg.g⁻¹ creat)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>≤10</td> <td>0.1</td> </tr> <tr> <td>11-20</td> <td>0.2</td> </tr> <tr> <td>21-30</td> <td>0.3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>31-40</td> <td>0.5</td> </tr> <tr> <td>41-50</td> <td>0.8</td> </tr> <tr> <td>>50</td> <td>1</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Age (years)	U-Cd (µg.g ⁻¹ creat)	≤10	0.1	11-20	0.2	21-30	0.3	31-40	0.5	41-50	0.8	>50	1	
Age (years)	U-Cd (µg.g ⁻¹ creat)																
≤10	0.1																
11-20	0.2																
21-30	0.3																
31-40	0.5																
41-50	0.8																
>50	1																
Additional Comments																	

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{GenPop}: numerical value of the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in µg.g⁻¹ creat

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV_{GenPop}: reflects the reliability of the proposed HBM-GV. The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study used, uncertainties related to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV).

An attribution of a global level of confidence is suggested for the proposed U-Cd HBM-GV_{GenPop}, considering the assessment of the various uncertainties:

- regarding the nature and quality of the Cd toxicological data: the database on Cd is based on a large number of both human and animal studies. → **high**
- regarding the critical endpoint and mode of action: the confidence in the evidence of effects on the renal function is high. The renal effects after exposure to Cd are well studied and the critical endpoint is supported by the clinical interpretation of markers of renal toxicity (EFSA, 2009). → **high**
- regarding the meta-analysis (EFSA, 2009) selected as the key study: the meta-analysis is based on 35 studies, however, included were only studies in which associations between urinary Cd (as an indicator of cumulative Cd exposure) and β₂M as one possible indicator of early nephrotoxic effects were examined. EFSA further adopted a chemical-specific adjustment factor of 3.9, which may be viewed as an assessment factor (AF) for intra-species variability. According to the CONTAM panel the reference point is consistent with earlier calculations in individual studies using other biomarkers of kidney and bone effects. → **high/medium**
- regarding PBPK modelling: to account for Cd accumulation in the human body throughout life, PBPK modelling was used to reconstruct urinary Cd concentrations at each age that lead to an urinary Cd concentration of 1 µg.g⁻¹ creat after 50-60 years. → **high**

The global level of confidence for U-Cd HBM-GV for the general population is set to “**high**”

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3) HBM-GV_{GenPop} status: the status value is fixed to 'provisional', thereby reflecting that this value could be revised later on in the project, if new data would be available.

4) HBM-GV_{GenPop} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{GenPop} in the HBM4EU workframe

5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS

http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf

6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:

https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if_/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/

7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.

8) Harmonised CLP classification: CLP classification including CMR and other health relevant effects. In the case that classification is not harmonised, this should be stated. For self-classifications by industry the ECHA- CLP inventory can be searched at: <http://echa.europa.eu/web/guest/information-on-chemicals/cl-inventory-database>

9) Molar mass: mass of Cd per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

10) Biomarker(s) identification: Monitoring of urinary cadmium (U-Cd) is recommended, U-Cd is a well-known and reliable indicator of long-term exposure to Cd.

11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarker(s) (expressed in g/mol)

17) Derivation method: examining associations between urinary Cd (as an indicator of cumulative Cd exposure) and β 2M as indicator of early nephrotoxic effects

18) Key study, type of study, POD: EFSA (2009), meta-analysis of 35 epidemiological studies. It is recognised that an urinary concentration of β 2M above of 300 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat is related to the first signs of tubular cytotoxicity that should be prevented. This is why this concentration is generally used as the threshold for Cd toxicity. A benchmark concentration was established by EFSA, which is suitable to prevent an excretion of β 2M that is elevated by 5% and the 95% lower confidence limit for this value was selected: 4 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat of urinary Cd (range of BMDL₅ for the statistical cut-off and biological cut-off value limit of 300 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat).

19) Assessment factors: EFSA adopted a chemical-specific adjustment factor of 3.9, which may be viewed as an assessment factor (AF) for intra-species variability, so that the inter-individual variance in sensitivity to Cd can be taken into consideration to an appropriate degree and to also protect groups of people who are sensitive. As a result a value of 1 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat has been derived which can be regarded as HBM-GV_{GenPop} for adults over 50 years of age:

20) PBPK modelling was used to reconstruct urinary Cd concentrations at each age that lead to an urinary Cd concentration of 1 $\mu\text{g.g}^{-1}$ creat after 50-60 years.

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10.2 Factsheet on the HBM-GV for workers

Compound: Cd			
Target population: Occupationally exposed adults			
Parameter	Note	Value / descriptor	Comments
HBM-GV _{Worker} and Status			
Target population: workers			
HBM-GV _{Worker}	1	U-Cd : 2 µg.g ⁻¹ creat B-Cd : 5 µg.L ⁻¹	
Level of confidence	2	Assumed to be high/medium	See note for explanation
HBM-GV _{Worker} status	3	Preliminary	
HBM-GV _{Worker} year of issue	4	2019	
General Information			
CLP-INDEX-Nr.	5		
EC-Nr.	6	231-152-8	
CAS-Nr.	7	7440-43-9	
Harmonised CLP classification	8	Carc. Cat. 1B (H350) Mut.2 (H341) Repr.1B (H361fd)	
Molar mass	9	112.41 g.mol ⁻¹	Cd metal
Biomarker(s)			
Identification	10	Biomarkers of exposure: U-Cd, B-Cd Biomarkers of effects: RBP and β2M	
Molar mass of biomarker(s)	11	Cd = 112.41 g.mol ⁻¹ RBP = 21.4 kDa β2M = 11.8 kDa	
Derivation method and HBM-GV _{Worker} calculation for biomarker 1: urinary Cd (U-Cd)			
Derivation method	17	Based on a relationship between U-Cd and markers of renal effects	
Key study, Author(s), Year	18	Chaumont et al. 2011	
Species	18	Human (workers)	
Route/type of study	18	Inhalation (and oral route)	
Exposure duration	18	Long-term exposure	
Critical endpoint	18	Renal toxicity	
POD value	18	U-Cd : 5.5 µg.g ⁻¹ creat	
Intraspecies and study duration adjustment	19	3	
Derivation method and HBM-GV _{Worker} calculation for biomarker 2 : blood Cd (B-Cd)			
Derivation method	20	Based on a relationship between B-Cd with markers of renal effects	

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Key study, Author(s), Year	21	ACGIH appraisal supported by Järup et al. 1988 study	
Species	22	Human (workers)	
Route/type of study	23	Inhalation (and oral route)	
Exposure duration	24	Long-term exposure	
Critical endpoint	25	Renal toxicity	
POD value	26	5.5 µg.L ⁻¹	
Interspecies and study duration adjustment		None	
Additional Comments			

Explanation of notes:

1) HBM-GV_{Worker}: numerical values for 2 biomarkers of exposure (U-Cd and B-Cd)

Monitoring of B-Cd is recommended in addition to U-Cd (especially for new employees at workplace) allowing to control the workers exposure to Cd in the short term.

2) Level of confidence of the HBM-GV:

The level of confidence takes into account the various uncertainties underlying the derivation of the HBM-GV (e.g. reliability of the key study, uncertainties related to toxicokinetic data on the substance of interest, to the extrapolations and calculation of the final HBM-GV).

An attribution of a global level of confidence is suggested for the proposed U-Cd HBM-GV_{Worker}, considering the assessment of the various uncertainties:

- regarding the nature and quality of the Cd toxicological data: the database on Cd is based on a large number of both human and animal studies → **high**
- regarding the critical endpoint and mode of action: the confidence in the evidence of effects on the renal function is high. The renal effects after occupational exposure to Cd are well studied and the critical endpoint is supported by the clinical interpretation of markers of renal toxicity (Bernard et al. 2004) → **high**
- regarding the selected key study for identification of the POD: the study was conducted in humans at the workplace, in a large population (n=599). The studied cohort was sufficiently large to allow estimation of threshold values for Cd-induced LMW proteinuria using data from never smokers only. However, the average age of workers was 45 years (+/- 10 years) so this value offers less protection to young workers → **medium**

The global level of confidence for U-Cd HBM-GV in the occupational field is set to **“high/medium”**

An attribution of a global level of confidence is suggested for the proposed B-Cd HBM-GV_{worker}, considering the assessment of the various uncertainties:

- regarding the nature and quality of the Cd toxicological data: the database on Cd is based on a large number of both human and animal studies → **high**
- regarding the critical endpoint and mode of action: the confidence in the evidence of effects on renal function is high. For B-Cd, the derivation of HBM-GV is based on the relationship between B-Cd and markers of renal toxicity → **medium**
- regarding the selected key study for identification of the POD: The HBM-GV_{worker} is based on ACGIH appraisal supported by a study (workplace study) → **medium**

The global level of confidence for B-Cd HBM-GV in the occupational field is set to **“high/medium”**

4) HBM-GV_{Worker} year of issue: year of setting the HBM-GV_{worker} in the HBM4EU workframe

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5) CLP Number: according to Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging (CLP) of substances and mixtures, implementing the globally harmonised system of chemical classification or GHS

http://guidance.echa.europa.eu/docs/guidance_document/clp_introduutory_en.pdf

6) EC Number: under European Inventory of Existing Commercial chemical Substances (EINECS), ELINCS (European List of Notified Chemical Substances) in support of Directive 92/32/EEC, the 7th amendment to Directive 67/548/EEC, NLP (No-Longer Polymers), see: ESIS: European chemical Substances Information System:

<https://web.archive.org/web/20131106181548if/http://esis.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

7) CAS Number: collection of disclosed chemical compound information by Chemical Abstracts Service. Almost all molecule databases can be searched by CAS Registry Number.

8) Harmonised CLP classification: The harmonised classification is available for the Cd but some compounds of Cd has an harmonised classification under CLP regulation (<https://echa.europa.eu/fr/information-on-chemicals/annex-vi-to-clp>)

9) Molar mass: mass of Cd per amount of this substance expressed in g/mol

10) Biomarker(s) identification: Monitoring of B-Cd is recommended in addition to U-Cd (especially for new employees at workplace) because it can be used to verify that exposure to Cd is adequately controlled in the short term

11) Molar mass of the biomarker(s): mass of the selected biomarker(s) (expressed in g/mol)

17) Derivation method: Based on human studies at the workplace and on the relationship between U-Cd levels and markers of renal effect levels

18) POD: It is accepted in different studies that an increase in urinary concentrations of β 2M and RBP above 1000 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat is related to irreversible tubular toxicity. It is also recognised that urinary concentration above 300 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat is related to the first signs of tubular cytotoxicity that should be prevented. This is why an urinary concentration for RBP and β 2M of 300 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ creat is generally used as the threshold for Cd toxicity.

Chaumont et al. 2011 gives a robust calculation of a BMD in a large population of workers using the response of the RBP and β 2M. In this study the average duration of employment is 18.8 years and the average age of workers is 45 years (\pm 10 year)

19) Despite the lack of data, it would be prudent to apply a safety factor. Therefore, an assessment factor for intraspecies differences (AF_H) of 3 can be applied by default to take into account the (low) average age in the key study. The aim is to protect older workers or workers with longer period of exposure.

20) Derivation method: Based on human studies at the workplace and on the relationship between B-Cd levels and markers of renal effect levels

21) ACGIH appraisal supported by Järup et al. (1988) study. The authors of this study examined the relationship between an index of cumulative exposure to cadmium corresponding to the weighted average blood concentration of cadmium, the exposure time and urinary excretion of β 2M in 440 workers (326 men, 114 women) in a battery plant.

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12 Annex

12.1 PBPK model for cadmium

The model PBPK proposed by Kjellstrom and Norberg (1978) was used with parameter values that were proposed by Ruiz et al. (2010) to interpret urinary concentrations of Cd in the US biomonitoring study NHANES. This model considers amount and flow between 8 compartments: lung, intestine, 3 blood compartments (plasma (B1), erythrocytes (B2) and metallothionein (B3)), liver, kidney and other tissues, and two excretion routes: faeces and urine. Originally, two exposure routes were included: inhalation and oral, but in this work, only the oral route was considered. This generic model was validated in Ruiz et al. (2010) by comparing simulations to other published model simulations and to human data sets (Choudhury et al., 2001, Diamond et al., 2003, Hays et al., 2008). Human physiological and chemical-specific parameters describing the absorption, distribution, and blood and tissue partitioning were taken from Kjellstrom and Norberg (1978) and Ruiz et al. (2010).

Evolution of body weight and renal function with age

Variability related to the modification of body weight and renal function with age was included in the model proposed by Ruiz et al., 2010. However, data were calibrated for a US population, which is quite different from the French population in terms of body weight. This is why a new equation for the evolution of the mean body weight was estimated based on French data commonly used for health risk assessments. Indeed, body weights from by the Second French Total Diet Study (TDS2, Arnich et al., 2012) was used regarding adults and children above 3 years old and data from the French infant total diet studies (ANSES - EATi, in progress), for children under 3 years old. These two datasets were combined and polynomial regression was applied using R software to determine the equation that describes the evolution of the mean body weight with the age. It results in the following equation that describes the evolution of the body weight expressed in kg with the age expressed in year:

$$\text{Mean body weight} = 3.68 + 4.47 * \text{year} - 0.093 * \text{year}^2 + 0.00061 * \text{year}^3$$

In the same way, the evolution of renal excretion was modelled combining data from the French Nutrition and Health Survey (ENNS, Castetbon et al., 2009) for adults and data from Remer et al. (2002) for children. A theoretical set of creat excretion data was built from these two different studies and is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Evolution of creat excretion with age based on the observed data from the French Nutrition and Health Survey (ENNS, Castetbon et al., 2009) for adults (>18) and data from Remer et al. (2012)

It results in the following equations that describes the evolution of the urinary creat excretion expressed in ug/g with the age in year (respectively for the 50th, 5th and 95th percentile):

$$Ucr_{p50} = 0.05 + 0.0221 * year + 8.962e-03 * year^2 - 4.486e-04 * year^3 + 7.476e-06 * year^4 - 4.168e-08 * year^5$$

$$Ucr_{p95} = 0.08 + 1.5e-01 * year - 2.802e-03 * year^2 + 1.7e-05 * year^3 - 8e-8 * year^4 + 8.489e-12 * year^5$$

$$Ucr_{p5} = 0.04 + 0.000012 * year + 7.6e-03 * year^2 - 4e-04 * year^3 + 7.35e-06 * year^4 - 4.55e-08 * year^5$$

Estimation of the age-based benchmark biological values

The modified PBPK model was then used to reconstruct urinary Cd concentrations at each age that lead to a urinary Cd concentration of 1 ug.g⁻¹ creat after 50-60 years. At constant rate of Cd intake, renal cortex Cd concentrations are predicted to reach a peak at age 55 years (ATSDR, 2012). The corresponding values are described in Figure 2 and provided for each age in Table 1, together with the mean body weight used in the model.

Figure 2: Cd urinary concentration (ug/g creat) as a function of age (year)

Table 1: Urinary Cd concentration (ug/g creat) predicted by the PBPK model to reach a value of 1 ug/g creat.

Time (year)	Body weight (kg)	CdU (ug/g creat)
0	4	0,00
1	8	0,03
2	12	0,06
3	16	0,08
4	20	0,09
5	24	0,10
6	27	0,11
7	31	0,12
8	34	0,13
9	37	0,13
10	40	0,14
11	42	0,15
12	45	0,16
13	47	0,16
14	50	0,17
15	52	0,18
16	54	0,19
17	56	0,20

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Time (year)	Body weight (kg)	CdU (ug/g creat)
18	58	0,21
19	59	0,22
20	61	0,23
21	62	0,24
22	64	0,25
23	65	0,26
24	66	0,27
25	67	0,28
26	68	0,30
27	69	0,31
28	69	0,33
29	70	0,35
30	71	0,36
31	71	0,39
32	71	0,41
33	72	0,43
34	72	0,46
35	72	0,48
36	73	0,51
37	73	0,54
38	73	0,57
39	73	0,60
40	73	0,63
41	73	0,67
42	73	0,70
43	72	0,73
44	72	0,76
45	72	0,80
46	72	0,83
47	72	0,86
48	71	0,88
49	71	0,91

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Time (year)	Body weight (kg)	CdU (ug/g creat)
50	71	0,93
51	71	0,95
52	70	0,97
53	70	0,98
54	70	0,99
55	70	0,99
56	69	1,00
57	69	1,00
58	69	1,00
59	69	0,99
60	69	0,99
61	69	0,98
62	69	0,98
62	69	0,98

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12.2 General information on blood cadmium (ANSES, 2018)

Name	Blood Cadmium B-Cd
Other substances giving rise to these biomarkers	None
Concentrations found in exposed workers or volunteers	<u>Field studies:</u> 1 to 170 µg.L ⁻¹ (range) <u>Studies in volunteers:</u> Not specified
Conversion factor	1 µg.L ⁻¹ = 0.009 µmol.L ⁻¹ 1 µmol.L ⁻¹ = 112.41 µg.L ⁻¹
Concentrations in the general population	USA-NHANES (2015-2016), CDC (2019) 95 th percentile: All: 1.22 µg.L ⁻¹ (1.07-1.37) - n=4988 Age 1-5 years: 0.160 µg.L ⁻¹ (0.140-0.180) - n=790 Age 6-11 years: 0.200 µg.L ⁻¹ (0.180-0.230) – n=1023 Age 12-19 years: 0.330 µg.L ⁻¹ (0.270-0.480) – n=565 Age > 20 years: 1.35 µg.L ⁻¹ (1.22-1.48) – n= 2610
	Germany-GerES (1998): n = 4822 people from the general population 95 th percentile: 3.32 µg.L ⁻¹ (smokers); 0.71 µg.L ⁻¹ (non-smokers) (Becker <i>et al.</i> , 2002)

12.3 General information on urinary cadmium

Name	Urinary cadmium (U-Cd)
Other substances giving rise to this biomarker	None
Concentrations found in exposed workers or volunteers	<u>Field studies:</u> 1 to 200 µg.g ⁻¹ of creat (range) <u>Studies in volunteers:</u> Not specified
Concentrations in the general population	USA-NHANES (2015-2016), CDC (2019) 95 th percentile: All: 0.781 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (0.675-0.906) - n=3058 Age 3-5 years: 0.227 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (0.179-0.278) - n=485 Age 6-11 years: 0.157 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (0.132-0.189) – n=379 Age 12-19 years: 0.147 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (0.120-0.187) – n=402 Age > 20 years: 0.882 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (1.22-1.48) – n= 1792 Smokers: 1.29 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (1.11-1.57) – n = 834 Age 18-49 years: 0.667 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.555-0.745) – n= 457 Age>50 years: 1.80 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (1.46-2.20) n = 377 Non-smokers: 0.775 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (0.608-0.924) – n=1468 Age 18-49 years: 0.405 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (0.358-0.521) – n= 748 Age>50 years: 0.961 µg.g ⁻¹ creat. (0.763-1.20) - n=720
	Germany-GerES (4822 people from the general population) 95 th percentile: 0.91 µg.g ⁻¹ creat (smokers); 0.61 µg.g ⁻¹ creat (non-smokers) (Becker <i>et al.</i> , 2003)

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	France-ENNS (2006-2007) (Fréry <i>et al.</i> , 2011) 95 th percentile: Age 18-39 years: 0.57 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.51-0.63) – n=562 Age 40-59 years: 0.95 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.88-1.02) – n=947 Age 60-74 years: 1.15 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(1.04-1.26) – n=421 Smokers: 0.79 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.69-0.89) – n=913 Age 18-39 years: 0.44 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.40-0.48) – n=254 Age 40-59 years: 0.79 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.63-0.95) – n=423 Age 60-74 years: 1.04 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.87-1.21) – n=236 Nonsmokers: 1 µg.g ⁻¹ creat.(0.92-1.08) – n=457
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12.4 Workplace studies describing blood cadmium concentrations related to concentrations of tubular toxicity markers reported in field studies

Jakubowski *et al.* (1987) performed a study on 102 Cd-exposed workers and 85 controls. The mean (geometric) concentration found in the controls was high at 4.8 µg Cd/L blood whereas the corresponding values in the exposed population ranged from 7.5 to 49 µg/L depending on the industrial sector.

Chia *et al.* (1989) studied certain parameters of renal dysfunction in a group of 65 women exposed to Cd compared to nine controls. The exposed women had a mean concentration of blood Cd (range) of 7.6 (1-26) µg/L whereas the corresponding values for the controls were 0.8 (0.2-1.4) µg/L. For urinary Cd, the concentrations were 1.73 (0.05-21) µg/L in the exposed population and 0.09 (0.02-0.2) µg/L in the controls. The authors noted a correlation between blood Cd and NAG excretion on the one hand and β2M excretion on the other hand. Urinary NAG excretion increased in subjects from 1 µg Cd/L blood.

Bernard *et al.* (1990) examined several parameters of nephrotoxicity in 58 workers in a non-ferrous smelter compared to the same number of controls. The geometric means (range) for Cd blood concentrations were respectively 0.89 (0.3-2.9) and 6.54 (1.6-51) µg/L in the control workers and exposed workers. When grouping together all of these subjects to study the prevalence of abnormal values for nephrotoxicity parameters as a function of blood Cd (<2; 2-5; 5-10 and >10 µg/L), the authors observed a statistically significant increase in abnormal values only in the >10 µg/L group for all of the nephrotoxicity parameters, suggesting a NOAEL between 5 to 10 µg/L (note that the thresholds for abnormal values used by the authors were respectively 324 and 240 µg.g⁻¹ creat for β2M and RBP).

Järup *et al.* (1988) examined the relationship between an index of cumulative exposure to Cd corresponding to the weighted average blood concentration of Cd multiplied by the exposure time and the urinary excretion of β2M in 440 workers (326 men, 114 women) in a battery plant. The authors showed that there was a correlation between this blood index of cumulative exposure and the other atmospheric index of cumulative exposure expressed in µg-years.m⁻³. They also showed a dose-response relationship between abnormal tubular proteinuria, defined as a β2M value above 311 µg.g⁻¹ creat, and the blood index of cumulative exposure. By interpolating from the graph in Figure 3b of the article, a 10% increase in abnormal proteinuria corresponds to approximately 12,500 nmol.months.L. For a work life of 30 to 40 years, this value corresponds to an average blood Cd concentration of 2.9 to 3.9 µg/L.

Roels *et al.* (1991) examined the GFR in workers exposed to Cd or previously exposed and retired at the time of the study, in addition to a control group. Of the 36 exposed subjects under the age of 50 years, none showed abnormal proteinuria defined as β2M > 300 µg.g⁻¹ creat, RBP > 300 µg.g⁻¹

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creat or albumin > 15 mg/g creat. Their average blood Cd concentration was 4.3 µg/L. In subjects over the age of 50 years, 31 exposed workers did not show abnormal proteinuria and their average blood Cd concentration was 3.2 µg/L. Twelve exposed workers over the age of 50 years had abnormal proteinuria and an average blood concentration of 7.5 µg/L.

Järup and Elinder (Järup *et al.*, 1995) examined the relationship between glomerular filtration rate and blood Cd concentrations in 42 welders exposed to Cd for at least five years. The authors reported a drop of 20% or more in GFR versus the normal expected value in 3.4%, 33% and 100% of subjects having a blood Cd concentration below 5.6 µg/L, between 5.6 and 8.4 µg/L and above 8.4 µg/L, respectively. This decrease in GFR was considered an irreversible phenomenon. The toxicokinetic model published by Nordberg and Kjellström (1979) was not used, since it has not been validated for Cd blood levels and occupational exposure.